

STARS
Technology Corporation

H2 SilverSTARS: Pilot Plant Demonstration at SunLine Transit Agency

Final Report

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Executive Summary

Preparing World-Record, Game Changing Technology for Commercial Applications

The H2 SilverSTARS project represents over 30 years and \$50 million in research and development at the Department of Energy’s Pacific Northwest National Laboratory (PNNL), with recent support from Southern California Gas Company (SoCalGas). This initiative has delivered breakthrough technology for carbon-negative hydrogen production using renewable natural gas distributed through the existing natural gas grid.

Pilot Plant Deployment at SunLine Transit Agency (SunLine)

Circled in red is the Chemical Reaction Module (CRM), which serves as the model for subsequent H2 Generators, plus additional subsystems and /components that were integrated with the STARS H2 Generator, including Xebec Pressure Swing Adsorption (PSA) system for H2 purification.

Key Achievements

- **Pilot Success:** A 24-month demonstration at SunLine Transit Agency advanced the STARS H₂ Generation System to near-commercial readiness (TRL 7).
- **Cost-Competitive Hydrogen:** Established a production and distribution pathway for clean hydrogen, integrated with the national natural gas grid, at a projected pump price between \$3/kg and \$5/kg, including consideration of the Clean Hydrogen Production Tax Credit, significantly lower than California’s current \$30–36/kg for hydrogen at filling stations.

- **World Record Efficiency:** Achieved an electrical-to-chemical energy conversion efficiency of 95% in the inductively-heated Steam-Methane Reformers (SMRs) during operation of the Pilot Plant at SunLine. This new record surpassed the previous record of 82% demonstrated with an inductively-heated STARS reformer in the laboratory at PNNL.
- **High Reliability:** Demonstrated over 90% uptime during the last year, with more than 1,000 hours of hydrogen production, including 100+ startups and a 300-hour continuous run.
- **Autonomous Operation:** Validated remote monitoring, autonomous control, redundancy in design, and safe shutdowns.
- **Validated Purity:** Independent laboratory confirmed compliance with national hydrogen purity standards for transit vehicles.

World-record, electrical-to-chemical energy conversion efficiency for inductively heated Steam-Methane Reforming (SMR).

95% Electrical-to-Chemical Efficiency was demonstrated during operation of the Pilot Plant at SunLine. This enables greater efficiency for overall H₂ production with substantially reduced carbon emissions compared to conventional, industrial SMRs.

Project Execution

- **Collaborative Approach:** Success was driven by strong coordination among SoCalGas, SunLine, STARS, and partners, with regular meetings and shared resources.
- **Engineering Excellence:** Barr Engineering led site design and FEED; PNNL and Oregon State University advanced the design of additively manufactured Steam-Methane Reformers and heat exchangers; HiLine Engineering fabricated and installed hardware.
- **Operational Integration:** STARS engineers optimized system controls and integration with the Xebec Pressure Swing Adsorption (PSA) and SunLine's hydrogen compressor.

Lessons and Next Steps

- **Design Improvements:** Operational data is guiding design upgrades for commercial hydrogen generators, including stable multi-reactor operation and improved component attachment.
- **Market Readiness:** Reliability and performance data support customer confidence and market uptake opportunities.
- **Scalable Solutions:** The next-generation Chemical Reaction Module will produce 250 kg/day of hydrogen in a compact footprint, with the ability to scale for larger needs.

Commercialization Roadmap

- **Immediate Goals:** Begin manufacturing 250 kg/day hydrogen generator modules, integrating SMRs and Water-Gas Shift (WGS) reactors, ready for deployment by end of 2026.
- **Strategic Partnerships:** Collaborating with hydrogen station constructors and operators, including joint proposals and agreements for mobile refueling projects.
- **Supporting California’s Hydrogen Vision:** Aligning with the ARCHES H2 Hub’s targets—5,000 fuel cell trucks and 1,000 buses, requiring 250 tonnes/day of hydrogen.
- **Deployment Plan:** Install 30 STARS H₂ Generator Systems in California and 30 more regionally over the next three years, with construction on each beginning by January 1, 2028. Each system will produce up to 1,500 kg H₂/day, addressing unmet demand from 17,000 fuel cell vehicles and supporting transit and trucking corridors.
- **Natural Gas Grid Integration:** Commercialization plan leverages and enhances the value of our nation’s multi-trillion-dollar natural gas grid.

Deployment of STARS H₂ Generators in three “tranches”, including ten California H₂ filling stations in each tranche.

STARS’ systems would be supplied with methane feedstock (renewable natural gas (RNG) and fossil natural gas) and would each be capable of producing up to 1500 kg of low-carbon hydrogen per day.

Ratepayer Benefits

The demonstrated ability of the STARS H₂ Generator to produce low-carbon, cost-competitive hydrogen could dramatically reduce the cost of clean renewable hydrogen that can be used to decarbonize hard-to-electrify sectors of the economy. Also, given that industrial hydrogen production is concentrated in communities identified by California Public Utilities Commission’s Environmental and Social Justice (ESJ) Action Plan, reduction of emissions from the STARS system can drastically benefit these communities if implemented at scale.

Conclusion

The SilverSTARS project has established a robust foundation for commercial, distributed hydrogen production. With proven technology, demonstrated cost advantages, and a clear path to market, STARS is positioned to accelerate the adoption of clean hydrogen across transportation sectors.

Acronyms and Abbreviations

AQMD	Air Quality Management District
ARL	adoption readiness level
Barr	Barr Engineering
CapEx	capital expenditures
CNG	compressed natural gas
CoFe	cobalt iron alloy
CRM	chemical reaction module
CPUC	California Public Utilities Commission
DOE	Department of Energy
EIA	U.S. Energy Information Administration
EPC	engineering, procurement, and construction
ESJ	environmental and social justice
FCV	fuel cell vehicle
GGE	gasoline gallon equivalent
HFCV	hydrogen fuel cell vehicle
HHV	higher heating value
HiLine	HighLine Engineering & Fabrication
HMI	human machine interface
HTR	high temperature recuperator
IRA	Inflation Reduction Act
MMPT	meso- and microchannel processing technology
MMBTU	million British Thermal Units
OpEx	operational expenditures
PHA	process hazard analysis
PLC	programmable logic controller
PNNL	Pacific Northwest National Laboratory
PSA	pressure swing adsorption
RAPID	Rapid Advancement in Process Intensification Deployment Institute
RNG	renewable natural gas

S/C	steam to carbon ratio
SMR	steam methane reforming
SoCalGas	Southern California Gas Company
STARS	STARS Technology Corporation
SunLine	SunLine Transit Agency
TRL	technology readiness level
WGS	water gas shift

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1.0 Project Overview

1.1 Background and Context

In the mid-1990s, researchers at Pacific Northwest National Laboratory (PNNL) explored the use of engineered microchannel structures to improve energy conversion and chemical processing equipment such as heat pumps, heat engines, chemical reactors, and chemical separators. Their pioneering work demonstrated significant potential for 1-2 orders of magnitude process intensification by overcoming heat- and mass-transfer limits found in conventional process systems. Over the following two decades, additional research and development projects at PNNL [1] [2] [3] [4] for federal agencies including the Department of Energy (DOE), the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA), the Army, and the Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA), led to over \$50M in project funding to proof-of-principle testing and new intellectual property development. These projects demonstrated and highlighted the opportunity to create highly efficient, compact microchannel reactions systems for hydrogen production.

This momentum, alongside similar activities in Europe, led to the launch of a periodic international conference on the prospects for microchannel process technology in the USA, Europe and, eventually Asia. It also spurred the formation of Rapid Advancement in Process Intensification (RAPID), organized and managed by DOE and the American Institute of Chemical Engineers.

In 1999, PNNL demonstrated the first microchannel reforming reactor. This was followed by the demonstration of a highly efficient modular microsystem process network, including four parallel microchannel reformers, each equipped with internal microchannel heat exchangers, plus additional microchannel heat exchangers for steam generation and recuperative preheating.

By the mid-2010s, PNNL's achievements included world record 70% solar-to-chemical efficiency [2] for hydrogen production, a milestone recognized by an R&D 100 Award in 2014 following a successful pilot-plant field demonstration at San Diego State University in Brawley, California. PNNL's microchannel technology innovations have received a total of five R&D 100 Awards.

Building on this foundation, several former PNNL researchers founded STARS Technology Corporation in late 2016, aiming to commercialize microchannel process technology for distributed hydrogen production in transportation and energy sectors. In subsequent years, STARS and PNNL partnered on R&D projects – funded by DOE and industry – to further develop these technologies, including 3D-printing of reactors and heat exchangers. By 2020, STARS began developing a modular hydrogen generator system utilizing inductive heating for the endothermic, steam-methane reforming reaction, based on additively manufactured components.

Southern California Gas Company (SoCalGas), recognized as a leading industry innovator on behalf of its ratepayers, has played a key role in these advancements. Its Research, Development, and Demonstration program has invested in hydrogen as a clean energy vector, partnering with DOE, PNNL, and STARS on projects such as the H₂ SilverSTARS project, which focuses on producing clean renewable hydrogen. The project, led and co-funded by the DOE, RAPID and STARS, was initiated in 2021 and broke ground in construction work at SunLine Transit Agency's facility in Thousand Palms, California, in August 2022.

SunLine, who has been a pioneer in adoption of hydrogen fuel and has had a hydrogen infrastructure on-site since 2000, provided the demonstration site facility with utilities and operation support. It also used the renewable hydrogen that the project produced to support on-site fueling of SunLine's fleet of hydrogen fuel cell buses.

At the core of the H2 SilverSTARS demonstration was the compact Chemical Reaction Module (CRM), also known as the reformer skid, which included three, inductively-heated steam methane reforming (SMR) reactors, three additively-manufactured, high temperature microchannel heat exchangers, two water-gas-shift (WGS) reactors, and additional microchannel exchangers. The Chemical Reaction Module and additional hardware, including a vapor-liquid separator, desulfurizer, steam generator and electrical and control systems were designed, procured and/or built by STARS' project team, including HiLine Engineering and Fabrication (HiLine), with extensive factory-testing by HiLine and STARS at HiLine's facilities in Richland, WA.

PNNL and Barr Engineering (Barr) provided additional, significant contributions. PNNL supported the adaptation of SMRs for induction heating, including simulation modeling and initial lab tests, and Barr provided initial conceptual design, including compilation of the Front-End Engineering & Design (FEED) package. Barr also provided the design for site work, which SoCalGas contracted to Burns & McDonnell, needed to set up, connect and operate the STARS system at SunLine.

STARS and HiLine delivered and set up the pilot system at the SunLine site in late 2022. In the 24-month period starting from 2023, STARS led the startup testing, commissioning and operation of the pilot production system, with SunLine and SoCalGas support, providing renewable hydrogen fuel for SunLine's fuel cell buses. The project included 1000 hours of hydrogen production and was completed in late 2024 with a 300-hour continuous test run.

1.2 SunLine Site Details

The H2 SilverSTARS demonstration was located inside SunLine Transit Agency's main facility in Thousand Palms, California, adjacent to I-10 interstate highway. The approximately 0.18-acre project site was inside the facility eastside fence. Outside the fence was a SunFuel Alternative Fuel Station that dispensed compressed hydrogen to support SunLine's fuel cell bus operation. The station also dispensed compressed natural gas to CNG vehicles and was open to the public.

At the northeast corner of the demonstration site, a metering station was connected to SoCalGas natural gas pipeline. Electrical power was provided by 480V/3Ph breaker panels at both north and south ends of the site. The facility's power was supplied by Southern California Edison from the Mirage Substation. A SunLine-owned deionized water system, located at the south end of the project site, was connected to municipal water mains. Industrial gases, such as nitrogen, were delivered by truck. Tail gas from the pilot plant was vented to atmosphere under a Rule 441 Research Permit granted by California South Coast Air Quality Management District.

The demonstration plant comprised several skid-mounted modules. The STARS pilot plant included a reformer process skid (the CRM, or Chemical Reaction Module), a steam generator, and an electrical skid that supplied electrical power and housed the control system. A small desulfurizer conditioned the natural gas feed stream. SoCalGas provided both an instrument air compressor and a pressure swing adsorption (PSA) skid – manufactured by Xebec – was used to separate and purify the hydrogen product stream.

SunLine's existing H₂ compression and distribution system was used to pressurize and deliver SilverSTARS hydrogen stream to an onsite H₂ refueling station.

1.3 Project Goals and Objectives

The project goal was to advance distributed production of clean hydrogen from renewable natural gas for fuel cell electric vehicles and other applications. This was accomplished through the demonstration project at SunLine Transit Agency.

The following major objectives support the achievement of this goal. They evaluate the readiness level of this technology within the research, development, demonstration, and deployment (RDD&D) continuum, and assess the benefits of work under this demonstration to the project partners (SoCalGas, SunLine, and STARS).

Advance the Technology Readiness Level

STARS developed and extensively tested the critical components of the hydrogen generator system, including the microchannel reactors and heat exchangers. A key objective of the current project was to advance the technology readiness level to TRL 7 by integrating the STARS components into a pilot plant and testing the prototype system in an operational environment with pipeline natural gas to produce hydrogen as fuel for transit buses. The technical and operational results from the demonstration provided valuable information necessary for designing the commercial version of the hydrogen generator.

Confirm and Improve the Value Proposition

The project team demonstrated the pilot plant's functional performance in producing fuel cell grade hydrogen in relevant quantities to support fueling operation of fuel cell buses at SunLine Transit. The project also demonstrated that the extended operation of such a hydrogen generator plant can be managed adequately with ease and at a high capacity factor. Furthermore, the utilities and raw material consumption data have enabled projection of the operating costs of the STARS commercial hydrogen generator. The demonstration has enabled us to design the commercial version of the system that will be deployable in 2026.

Establish Mature Resources for a Successful Business Ecosystem

In planning and executing this demonstration project, we significantly de-risked the technology. This includes demonstrating that the STARS hydrogen solution can be implemented with established project development, integration, and management processes such as practiced within an EPC contract framework. We have also demonstrated that existing physical and digital infrastructures at a fleet operator such as SunLine Transit adequately support the deployment of the distributed system. This includes natural gas pipeline, power, water, merchant gases delivery, chemical lab services, and industrial broadband etc. Lastly, this project helped to develop the manufacturing and supply chain needed to deploy the first-of-its-kind STARS system on a commercial scale.

Map the Terrain of License-to-Operate

The demonstration project qualified for a few exceptions in regulatory, permitting and siting, environmental and safety requirements due to the developmental nature of the project and the less-than-full-scale production. One objective of the project was to map out the full requirements for a commercial production system. The project also provided an opportunity to gauge local community perception via project publicity as well as industry acceptance through interactions with SunLine and participation in industry conferences as presenters and exhibitors.

Deliver Benefits to Project Participants' Customers

STARS advanced the technology and adoption readiness levels of its hydrogen generator system by testing it in an operational environment. SunLine provided benefits to its customers and the commercial transportation industry by demonstrating an advanced technology that reduces hydrogen fuel costs and helps ensure a reliable supply of onsite fuel for fleets. SoCalGas supported its ratepayers by reducing the cost of clean renewable hydrogen that can be used to decarbonize hard-to-electrify sectors of the economy and reducing emissions to benefit ESJ communities where industrial hydrogen production is concentrated.

1.4 Pilot Plant Project Accomplishments – Achieving Distributed Hydrogen Production from the Natural Gas Grid

The following bullets provide a summary of the individual accomplishments that brought the technology up to TRL-7 and ARL-7. These accomplishments support the conclusion that the commercial design of the STARS hydrogen generator will successfully compete in the marketplace. They provide the information needed to design and fabricate mass-producible, commercial systems, and demonstrate the path to distributed production of affordable hydrogen from the natural gas grid.

Specific accomplishments include:

- First lab-testing of inductively-heated microchannel SMRs at PNNL, achieving greater than 80% (world-record) electrical-to-chemical efficiency.
- First field demonstration of Steam-Reforming Reaction Modules, combining multiple microchannel SMR reactors with inductive heating, Water-Gas Shift (WGS) reactors and other microchannel heat exchangers, at Technology Readiness Level 7.
- Successful integration, shakedown testing and operation of all systems, including the STARS-supplied hardware with SoCalGas-supplied hardware and site hardware at the SunLine site.
- Demonstration of high reliability (greater than 90%), autonomous operations including normal and emergency shutdown without operator intervention, and the ability to remotely monitor and control hydrogen production through a secure cloud.
- Successful completion of 1000 hours of hydrogen production, over 100 startups, and a 300-hour continuous hydrogen production run.

Collectively, these pilot plant achievements support the design and deployment of compact, mass-producible, steam reforming Chemical Reaction Modules, for the daily production of 250 kilograms H₂ per module. Each module would occupy a footprint of approximately 1 m², about the size of a “vending machine”. Six such modules, together with supporting hardware including Pressure Swing Adsorption (PSA) for hydrogen purification, could produce 1500 kg H₂ per day.

The resulting mass-produced systems are anticipated to form the foundation of STARS’ commercial hydrogen generating infrastructure. When deployed on the gas grid, these systems enable distributed production of low- or zero-carbon hydrogen from RNG, at a projected levelized production cost of approximately \$5-6/kg, based on typical costs in California.

2.0 Methodology

This project was carried out in three phases: (1) Design and Assembly, (2) Setup and Shakedown Testing, and (3) Qualification and Commercial Operation. The project logic for each of these phases is illustrated in the diagrams shown in Figure 1 to Figure 3 below.

Figure 1. Overview of the H2 SilverSTARS project logic for the Design and Assembly phase.

Figure 2. Overview of the H2 SilverSTARS project logic for the Setup and Shakedown Testing phase.

Figure 3. Overview of the H2 SilverSTARS project logic for the Qualification and Commercial Operation phase.

The following are some of the key project activities marking the delivery of critical design, hardware, qualification, or test data.

- Front-end engineering design, licensing, and fabrication – The design of the hydrogen generator system and site preparation were accomplished during this phase. SoCalGas obtained a Rule 441 Research Permit from South Coast Air Quality Management District (AQMD). Control logic development and factory acceptance testing prior to shipping the hardware to SunLine were completed.
- Site preparation and installation of hardware – Conduit and underground piping were installed. The hardware was delivered to the site and after completing the installation, each subsystem was tested prior to conducting the full system test.
- System familiarization and optimization – The system that was installed at SunLine had limited operating history. The control systems needed to be modified to improve ease of operation and transient response. Some physical configuration changes were also made to improve operational performance. At the end of this phase, the systems were well integrated, and the sequencing algorithms were confirmed to operate appropriately.
- Integration of the PSA – Once the process skid optimization was completed, the integration of the PSA was started. A dewpoint sensor was added to the system to verify the moisture content in the hydrogen product from the PSA. The integration was completed upon successfully passing the SAE J2719 purity test as analyzed by an independent laboratory.
- Integration of the hydrogen compressor – An interface between the process skid and compressor was designed and field installed. The syngas flow transmitter was removed and recalibrated so that it could be relocated to the inlet of the compressor. These changes enabled monitoring of the hydrogen flow to the buses.
- Reliability and endurance testing – After the integration of the systems was complete, the project began a series of daily operating runs of about 12 hours from startup to shutdown. When the storage system was available, hydrogen was sent to the buses. Otherwise, the hydrogen was vented from the compressor skid. A few overnight operating cycles were conducted using the secure cloud to monitor and control the system remotely. A 300-hour continuous endurance run was successfully completed. This culminating run demonstrated the system's reliability and enabled completion of over 1000 hours production of hydrogen at SunLine. The field demonstration ended in October 2024.
- Decommissioning at end of project. In early June of 2025 the decommissioning of the site was completed. The site was restored to a condition that was acceptable to SunLine and all hardware skids were removed.

2.1 Pilot Plant Design and Fabrication

A front-end engineering design (FEED) approach was used in the project. The first step in the process is to identify the design criteria including establishing the desired performance goals, regulatory and engineering standards. Preliminary design alternatives were considered and some concessions in the design and schedule were necessary due to equipment supply issues during the COVID-19 pandemic. Interactions among the design engineers, the fabricators, and both STARS and SoCalGas ensured that the design and fabrication would meet the needs of the project. As a result of these interactions, the project scope, approach, and level of effort were modified as the process proceeded.

When the piping and instrumentation drawings were completed, a multi-disciplined process hazard analysis (PHA) review of the design was conducted to identify and mitigate potential failure modes of the hardware. This valuable exercise helped to verify that adequate mitigations were in place in the final design to safely respond to anomalies and bring the system to a safe shutdown under all anticipated failure modes.

The initial proposal work scope included constructing two 165 kg/day hydrogen process skids. However, during the FEED development it became clear that the costs and risks associated with producing a full-scale production capability would not be possible with the available project funding. Several design configurations were considered. As a result of the FEED process the decision was made to design the pilot system at half of the original scale with an option to build a second half if there were sufficient project funds available after validating and modifying the pilot production performance.

STARS' initial cost estimates were based on experience with previous microchannel reaction systems plus Department of Energy numbers for some additional components (e.g., mechanical compressors) but did not adequately cover the non-recurring engineering costs. In addition, there was no way to anticipate the cost or schedule impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic, which was just hitting the USA as the project began. As a result, it became clear during the FEED exercise and in late 2020 that there would not be sufficient funding to construct more than a smaller scale system with a production capacity of about 70 kg/day.

Barr Engineering was awarded the contract to design the pilot system, and HiLine Engineering and Fabrication was awarded the contract to fabricate the system. During this timeframe, a Cooperative Research and Development Agreements (CRADA) project among the Pacific Northwest National Laboratory (PNNL), the RAPID Institute, Oregon State University, and STARS were also used to support the design of the reactors and heat exchangers that would be used in the system. PNNL did the material and stress analysis for design of the reactors. Work performed jointly by PNNL and OSU informed the design for additive manufacturing.

There were several challenges that needed to be addressed in the development of the pilot system. Previous designs of the microchannel SMR were two-layer designs – a reaction layer that held the catalyst and a return layer that helped recuperate and distribute temperature. The pancake reactor had been designed to be heated by a solar concentrating parabolic mirror. At the beginning of the project, STARS and SoCalGas decided to heat the SMR reactors using induction heating rather than a solar concentrator. This necessitated changes in the design of the SMR reactors.

The decision was made to add a third layer to the reactor so that induction heat could be applied to both sides of the pancake reactor. The three-layer reactor design changed the thermal stress characteristics of the reactor. Analysis of the stresses led to a design modification and a pending patent, intellectual property that has been licensed to STARS from PNNL.

The three-layer SMR reactors in the pilot system are constructed of Haynes 282 alloy which is not ferromagnetic. This was a major challenge for implementing the induction heating of the reactors. Surrogates for the reactor and induction generators were used to develop the design. Several configurations were explored until we achieved a satisfactory design for the induction interface. The design of the reactors for the SunLine pilot system uses cobalt-iron (CoFe) radials, which have a high magnetic susceptibility at SMR temperatures and are brazed to the reactor body. These radials pull in the magnetic field from the induction system to heat the reactor shell. The induction interface set a new world record for electrical to chemical energy conversion efficiency of 82% as measured by PNNL, based on the ratio of the increase in higher heating value in the reacting stream to the electrical power provided to the induction system, including microelectronics. Previous research publications on the inductive heating of SMRs had reported efficiencies of less than 25% and predicted that substantial improvements would take intensive research and development. Our effort therefore demonstrated both the advantage of applying inductive heating to microchannel process components as well as the strength of the team which has considerable experience in developing thermally efficient microchannel process technology. STARS, independent of PNNL, developed the induction interface and has U.S. and foreign patents pending for these design enhancements.

Another challenge during the fabrication was the design of the steam generation process. We had originally intended to use a microchannel catalytic combustor – such as had previously been demonstrated at PNNL in the late 1990s; however, SoCalGas requested that we not include catalytic combustion in the process. As a result, in late 2020, we decided to attempt to expand on an electrically heated steam generator that had first been used in the previous solar thermochemical demonstration at the San Diego State University Brawley Campus [2] [3].

In the initial assembly of the pilot system at HiLine, three of these heaters were installed in parallel. However, factory testing of this configuration resulted in serious flow imbalances making the configuration unacceptable. Commercial steam generators were not available off the shelf, and the COVID-19 pandemic was making it difficult to get a commitment for delivery in under six months. As a result, engineers at HiLine designed and built the electrically heated steam generator and superheater section that was used in the pilot system. STARS considered but chose not to design an extensive thermal recuperation network within the pilot system. There were several factors that influenced this decision. The recuperation added engineering and hardware complexity to the system configuration that would have added costs to the system. There were also control system challenges with implementing the design. Conveniently, a cooling tower onsite was deemed adequate for heat rejection.

Another challenge involved cooling the induction heating coils. The induction coils are physically located 11 millimeters from the SMR reactors. The operating temperature of the reactor is up to 800°C. The maximum operating temperature of the induction coils is 185°C. This challenge involved finding suitable thermal insulation material and providing adequate cooling to keep the induction coils from overheating. Both challenges were eventually overcome.

The heaters on the reactors in the pilot system used a commercial induction system, supplied by E.G.O. Group (a European company with a US subsidiary) for commercial kitchens. The system is highly reliable and operates with high efficiency but is not designed to support STARS' full power induction needs. The manufacturer has developed an 8-kilowatt (kW) induction generator, but it did not yet have an interface that would work with the pilot control system. Therefore, we chose to work with the 5 kW E.G.O. induction generators that could be interfaced. The decision to go with the lower power generator reduced the syngas production potential but saved the cost and time to develop and test a new control interface.

A period of 28 months elapsed from the issuance of the contract until the delivery of the pilot test system to SunLine. The design process took approximately 8 months. Hardware fabrication took an additional 12 months during which time the induction process for the new SMR reactors was being validated through testing at PNNL. Factory testing and control system tuning added an additional 8 months before the system was ready to be delivered to SunLine.

Figure 4. SolidWorks model illustrations of overall Chemical Reaction Module: front view (left) and back view (right).

Figure 5. SolidWorks model illustrations of overall Chemical Reaction Module: isometric front view (left) and isometric back view (right).

Figure 6. Demonstration site construction and equipment assembly at SunLine in September 2022: site preparation completed (left) and process and electrical skids installed (right).

2.2 Plant Operation and Data Collection

2.2.1 Startup Testing and Initial Commissioning

After onsite construction of the pilot plant was completed, startup testing and pre-commissioning checks were done to prepare for actual commissioning. This included bump tests of pumps and motors, pipeline purging, electrical panel energization, communication checks, control loop and wiring check, etc., to ensure the plant equipment can be operated safely. Process feed and utilities systems such as deionized water, natural gas, cooling water, instrument air, and auxiliary gas supplies were then checked and brought online.

The commissioning task was organized in several steps divided according to process flow. The first major equipment to commission was the STARS Chemical Reaction Module and associated skid equipment. First, the electrical boiler and steam generator were function-tested at full flow. After pressure leak check and system wide nitrogen purge, the reformer skid was energized by dry heating to a relatively low temperature set point for an initial run-in period. This was to verify that process heating functioned normally with the electrical induction system. A catalyst reduction step was then carried out at moderate temperature to condition the SMR reactors before operating the reformer at normal temperature and pressure conditions. The natural gas and steam feed flows to the reformer were increased gradually to production set points. The stable operation of recycle stream to feed water was also verified. The syngas product was vented to atmosphere and its composition was obtained using an online infrared gas analyzer. The Chemical Reaction Module became operational when syngas production was verified to match the expected capacity and production compositions based on prior subsystem level test data.

The PSA skid was commissioned next. The Xebec G2 system used rotary valves driven by a motor to control cycle speed. Significant problems were initially encountered with the PSA control algorithms. However, investigations identified inconsistencies in the PSA software code. After corrections by STARS engineers in the field, the PSA system was made to function adequately.

The initial step of PSA commissioning was to power up its own control panel and check communication with main process PLC. After PSA motor control and bed pressurization with reformer syngas were successfully verified, the two main operating parameters, i.e., cycle speed and hydrogen product backpressure were adjusted while maintaining a target syngas supply flow from the reformer. The tradeoff between hydrogen recovery and purity, which is always present in such PSA system, was considered in selecting a final operating set point. As a part of the PSA commissioning, a control logic to avoid excessive backpressure to the Chemical Reaction Module in the event of hydrogen offtake flow upset was also developed. Startup and shutdown procedures tailored to a fixed-flow syngas supply were also developed. The PSA commission work concluded when the above operating parameters and additional control logic were identified and implemented.

Integrated operation of the hydrogen compressor skid with the production system was commissioned last. An existing diaphragm compressor package at SunLine was brought back into service. The commissioning of this equipment was centered around establishing process control communications with the main process skids and setting the correct hydrogen pressure at the compressor inlet. Procedures for integrated operation startup and shutdown were established. Control logics to accommodate intermittency in compressor load and hydrogen offtake were also identified. The initial commissioning of the pilot plant

ended with the integrated system of reformer, PSA, and H₂ compressor skids operating on continuous process streams from natural gas and steam to purified and compressed hydrogen.

2.2.2 Process Tuning and Production Acceptance

At the STARS reformer, process tuning was aimed at reducing energy consumption and maximizing syngas production rate. There is a tradeoff between conversion and energy consumption. A higher steam to carbon ratio improves SMR conversion by shifting chemical reaction equilibrium but at the expense of more electrical power consumption for steam generation. Higher SMR reactor temperatures also favor higher conversion and energy efficiencies within the SMRs, but heat losses can also increase. The syngas production rate ultimately was limited by the power capacity of the reactor's inductive heating coupling so there was also a minor tradeoff between allocating heating power to proportionally higher process flow and allocating to operating the reactor at a higher temperature.

At the PSA skid, only limited tuning was possible because of a sizing mismatch between the PSA and the Reaction Module. The Xebec PSA was sized for a substantially larger flow rate, about five times that of the Chemical Reaction Module. This constraint significantly narrowed the usable range of the PSA cycle speed to the low end. Therefore, no extensive tuning of the PSA was planned. Instead, the focus was placed on ensuring stable integrated operation of the PSA in presence of fluctuations in syngas supply and hydrogen offtake that occurred in normal operation of the reformer and the compressor unit.

The compliance of the demonstration test operation with California air quality regulations required a stationary source emissions test to quantify the amount of CO and volatile organic emissions under normal process conditions. Conducting the source test by approved method and reporting the results allowed the project to operate the demonstration site under the Rule 441 Research Permit issued by California South Coast AQMD.

The pilot plant was accepted by SunLine for hydrogen production after purity analyses confirmed that the contaminant levels such as CO and moisture, etc., in the product stream meet the requirements by SAE J2719:2020 (ISO 14687:2019) for hydrogen fuel. The analyses were conducted by a qualified third-party laboratory with test reports referencing the above fuel standards.

2.2.3 Extended Operation and Performance Measurements

During the extended operation period, the pilot plant was kept in production mode to generate hydrogen for SunLine buses whenever onsite staffing, maintenance, and hydrogen offtake schedules allowed. A total of more than 1000 hours of system operation was targeted to measure hydrogen production rate, purity, energy and material consumption. When SunLine bus fueling was possible, the delivered hydrogen rate was also measured. In addition, events of process upsets and system recovery were also documented.

2.3 Data Analysis

Both steady state and transient process data were collected during the roughly 20-month period in which the pilot plant was shakedown tested and operated. The various types of data recorded and their analysis are summarized below.

2.3.1 Material Balance

Data acquisition by the PLC control system recorded the mass flows of feed water and natural gas, the dry syngas compositions, and the mass flow of the hydrogen product after PSA. Routine pressure leak tests were performed before every test run so that a simple mass balance calculation can be done to derive the component mass flows in the hot syngas, based on the measured dry syngas composition and stoichiometries of steam methane reforming and water gas shift reactions.

The component mole fractions y_i are indexed from 1 to 5 for H_2 , CH_4 , CO , CO_2 , and H_2O respectively. A syngas analyzer provided the gas mole fractions on dry gas basis y_i' ($i = 1$ to 4). The conversions of SMR and WGS reactions are expressed on feed methane basis as x_1 and x_2 , respectively. Assuming that the concentrations of other minor hydrocarbon components such as ethane are negligible, the conversions are calculated according to the equations below.

$$x_1 = (y_3' + y_4') / (y_2' + y_3' + y_4') \quad (\text{SMR conversion}) \quad (3)$$

$$x_2 = y_4' / (y_2' + y_3' + y_4') \quad (\text{WGS conversion}) \quad (4)$$

The steam-to-carbon ratio, s , is the molar ratio of steam to methane in the feed stream if other hydrocarbons are negligible. In pilot plant tests, the steam-to-carbon ratio was directly calculated from the feed water flow meter reading and the natural gas mass flow controller set point. The feed water flow meter reading was typically noisy due to the reciprocal action of the feed water pump. However, the average reading normally tracked the flow set point of the feed water pump very well. Therefore, in the steam-to-carbon ratio calculations, both water and natural gas flow set points were used in place of actual flow readings.

$$s = \dot{n}_{FW} / \dot{n}_{NG} \quad (5)$$

The hot syngas compositions are calculated from simple mass balance and reaction stoichiometries.

$$y_1 = (3x_1 + x_2) / (1 + s + 2x_1) \quad \text{H}_2 \quad (6)$$

$$y_2 = (1 - x_1) / (1 + s + 2x_1) \quad \text{CH}_4 \quad (7)$$

$$y_3 = (x_1 - x_2) / (1 + s + 2x_1) \quad \text{CO} \quad (8)$$

$$y_4 = x_2 / (1 + s + 2x_1) \quad \text{CO}_2 \quad (9)$$

$$y_5 = (s - x_1 - x_2)/(1 + s + 2x_1) \quad \text{H}_2\text{O} \quad (10)$$

The syngas molar flow, \dot{n}_{SG} , can be related to the natural gas feed flow, \dot{n}_{NG} , assuming there is no leakage in the reactor unit.

$$\dot{n}_{SG} = \dot{n}_{NG}(1 + s + 2x_1) \quad (11)$$

The hydrogen product flow coming out of the PSA skid was measured by a mass flow meter. The PSA skid hydrogen recovery, Y_{PSA} , is simply the ratio of the measured H₂ molar flow, \dot{n}_{H_2} , and the H₂ component flow in the supplied syngas.

$$Y_{PSA} = \dot{n}_{H_2}/(y_5\dot{n}_{SG}) = (\dot{n}_{H_2}/\dot{n}_{NG})/(s - x_1 - x_2) \quad (12)$$

The actual plant water consumption rate was lower than the feed water rate to the reactor unit because most of the excess steam was condensed downstream and recycled. The recycle stream was controlled by the binary logic of a drain valve that regulated the liquid level in the vapor liquid separator tank. The resulting recycle water flow was intermittent. When the drain valve was open, the feed water pump was supplied entirely by the recycle water stream. When the drain valve was closed, the steam generator was supplied by the makeup water stream. The time-averaged makeup water flow rate, or the actual plant water consumption rate, \dot{n}_{H_2O} , was calculated based on the duty cycle of the drain valve, D_{VLS} .

$$\dot{n}_{H_2O} = \dot{n}_{FW}(1 - D_{VLS}) \quad (13)$$

2.3.2 Energy Balance and Efficiencies

The projected operating expense of a hydrogen production plant such as the pilot plant crucially depends on the energy efficiency of the chemical conversion process. Analyses of energy balance can be done around different boundaries within the plant but one of the most important among them is the efficiency of the inductively heated SMR reactors as most of the energy input to the system is supplied to this reactor in form of induction heating. A similar analysis around the high-temperature recuperator (HTR) heat exchangers is also useful as this component handles the largest temperature differentials in the entire system. A gross energy balance of the whole plant is also necessary to ground the process economics.

The SMR reactors operated around 750°C to 800°C. Conduction through piping and insulation, convective loss at insulation surface, and direct radiative loss to ambient air and surrounding equipment all contributed to the overall heat loss at the reactors. High performance insulation designed for these reactors helped to manage the heat loss to an acceptable level. The reactor heat duty, Q_{SMR} , was calculated from reactant and product enthalpy flows.

$$Q_{SMR} = \dot{n}_{SG}h_{SG} - \dot{n}_{FG}h_{FG} \quad (14)$$

where \dot{n} is the stream molar flow rate, h is the stream molar enthalpy estimated from stream composition, temperature, and pressure, and subscripts SG and FG represent syngas product and feed reactant gas to the SMR, respectively.

The energy balance around the SMR reactor relates the above reactor heat duty, the induction heating input, Q_{IH} , and the heat loss at the reactor, Q_{LOSS} .

$$Q_{SMR} = Q_{IH} - Q_{LOSS} \quad (15)$$

High-temperature thermochemical systems such as the SMR reactors have been observed to follow an approximate first-order relationship between the energy input and output, characterized by a constant energy conversion over a wide range of heat duties and by a fixed heat loss term representing the parasitic heat loss at zero heat duty. This approximation worked well for concentrated solar receivers including a previous prototype of the SMR reactor that was field tested with concentrated solar heating. [2] Our extended operation at SunLine allowed the plotting of an operation line for our inductively-heated SMRs, providing an estimate of the fixed heat loss term and to provide a measure on the performance of the thermal design, as reported in Section 3.3.

There are several energy efficiency measures that are useful to evaluate the performance of the reactors. One is the thermal energy efficiency, η_T , that simply measures how much induction heat is captured by the increase in stream enthalpy:

$$\eta_T = Q_{SMR}/Q_{IH} \quad (16)$$

An electrical-to-chemical energy efficiency, η_{HHV} , measures the conversion of electrical energy supplied to the induction heater to the increase in the higher heating values of the product stream from the feed stream:

$$\eta_{HHV} = (\dot{n}_{SG}HHV_{SG} - \dot{n}_{FG}HHV_{FG})/P_{IH} \quad (17)$$

where HHV is the molar higher heating value of the stream and P_{IH} is the electrical power drawn by the induction heating system, including microelectronics.

The efficiency of a component or a system can also be evaluated by the second law of thermodynamics. The exergy efficiency of the SMR reactor, $\eta_{EX,SMR}$, is defined as the total exergy output divided by the total exergy input.

$$\eta_{EX,SMR} = (\dot{n}_{SG}B_{SG})/(\dot{n}_{FG}B_{FG} + P_{IH}) \quad (18)$$

where B is the molar exergy content of the stream including both the thermomechanical exergy and the chemical exergy. For exergy calculation, we chose the reference environment as 25°C and 1 atm with chemical compositions as proposed by Szargut et al. [5] Electrical energy can be considered as pure exergy for practical purposes so that P_{IH} , the electrical power supplied to the induction heater, is used as one of the exergy input.

The exergy efficiency of the HTR heat exchanger is defined based on thermomechanical exergy only because of the absence of chemical changes.

$$\eta_{EX,HTR} = (\dot{n}_{SG}B_{SG,HTR\ out} + \dot{n}_{FG}B_{FG,HTR\ out})/(\dot{n}_{SG}B_{SG,HTR\ in} + \dot{n}_{FG}B_{FG,HTR\ in}) \quad (19)$$

The total plant power consumption was estimated from energy meter readings and component heat duty data such as the induction heaters and the steam boiler. Real time power data on auxiliary equipment such as cooling tower pump, deionized water pumps, and air compressor were not available. The power consumption of such equipment was estimated based on nameplate power and estimated duty cycles.

2.3.3 Operation Performance Measures

As a pilot plant in demonstration testing, the system went through frequent startup and shutdown cycles with various lengths of continuous operations in between. The overall on-stream operation was tracked by cumulative hours while the system was at operating temperatures for reforming a natural gas feed stream. A separate time was tracked for continuous operation during the extended production phase of the project. A capacity factor was also estimated during this period to account for unexpected outage due to process upsets and equipment related issues.

2.4 Project Timeline and Milestones

Table 1. List of project milestones.

Milestone	Description	Completion
M1	Project Start	4/1/2020
M2	Deliver Integrated Gantt Chart Schedule	5/31/2020
M3	Initiate Assembly of Skid Hardware	1/1/2021
M4	Deliver Skid Hardware to SoCalGas	9/1/2022
M5	Commission Skid System	5/24/2023
M6-M11	Deleted Milestones per Amendment 3	6/12/2023
M12	Support Xebec PSA Commissioning Plus Initiate Three Months Operational Support at SunLine Transit	3/25/2024
M13	Initiate First Month Operational Support	4/2/2024
M14	Submit First Month Operational Support Progress Report	5/20/2024
M15	Submit Second Month Operational Support Progress Report	6/7/2024
M16	Submit Third Month Operational Support Progress Report	7/2/2024

Table 2. Activities and completion dates.

Date	Activities
2020-04-01	Contract signed with SoCalGas
2020-05-01	Contract with Barr Engineering (Project Management, Skid Design Development, Skid Fabrication Review and Testing Assistance, Commissioning Support)
2020-07-01	Front End Engineering Development Package completed
2020-11-01	Contract signed with Barr Engineering for site construction
2020-12-01	Contract in place for 3D printing of reactors
2021-01-01	Procurement of hardware for process skid
2021-01-01	Vapor liquid separator fabricated
2021-02-01	Construction begins on process skid
2021-07-01	SolidWorks design of process skid finalized
2021-12-01	Tuning of control algorithms begins
2021-12-01	Preliminary heating test of single reactor begins
2021-12-01	Process Hazard Analysis of process skid completed
2022-01-01	Construction of induction coil assembly completed
2022-01-01	Steam Generator design completed and connected to process skid
2022-02-01	Begin shop testing and tuning of control system
2022-07-01	Updated PHA to Include SunLine site system integration
2022-09-01	STARS hardware delivered to SunLine
2022-12-01	STARS Skid begins site testing
2023-01-01	H2 SilverSTARS unveiling ceremony at SunLine
2023-01-12	IR gas analyzer online
2023-04-04	Backpressure regulator installed on syngas line
2023-04-05	Setup for remote operation
2023-05-24	PSA integration completed -- repaired software and components
2023-06-01	Removed reactors to replace Co-Fe radials with new braze process
2023-09-01	Installed control system interface to compressor
2023-10-01	Recalibrated and reinstalled syngas flow sensor for H ₂
2023-10-01	Reinstalled reactors with new CoFe radials and began operating
2023-12-01	Replace HMI display to support hydrogen to PSA and compressor
2024-01-27	Installed dewpoint sensor on hydrogen product gas stream
2024-03-25	Begin hydrogen deliveries to the buses at SunLine
2024-10-01	Completed 300-hour continuous operation testing
2024-10-19	Completed 1000 hours cumulative operation

3.0 Technical Results

3.1 Hydrogen Production Rate

In steady state operation, the reformer output was about 53 kg-H₂/day, measured at the syngas product flow. The purified hydrogen product flow after the PSA was about 32 to 38 kg-H₂/day. Thus, the PSA performed at about 60% hydrogen recovery. This is significantly lower compared to the PSA design recovery of 83%, but is reasonable considering that the current operating point is at a little less than 25% of the PSA design flow. To maintain the hydrogen product design pressure, we had to operate the PSA rotary valve at the very low end of its speed range. The maximum recovery achievable was reduced as a result.

At the SunLine demonstration site, the ability of its downstream storage to accept hydrogen product from the H₂ generator pilot plant can fluctuate hourly depending on how fast the fuel cell bus fleet was drawing down the H₂ storage tanks. When the storage tank was full and no bus was refueling, the hydrogen product from the pilot plant had to be vented to the atmosphere at the compressor inlet. Without the compressor providing suction, most of the syngas going into the PSA would pressurize the adsorption beds and then vent through the PSA exhaust.

When the fully integrated system was operated, i.e., purified hydrogen from reformer and PSA being compressed and sent to the storage facility, the efficiency and capacity of the downstream compression unit could still limit the overall hydrogen delivery rate. We experienced reduced H₂ delivery flow when the SunLine compressor operated against the highest backpressure at the storage tank or when high ambient temperatures reduced the compressor efficiency. In the commercial design, better integration of hydrogen production with compression and storage should allow the CRM and PSA to operate at peak rate without the need to turn down or to vent valuable product. Attention should also be given to designing the hydrogen compression and storage systems to handle the full capacity of the production unit.

Looking forward to the next generation design for a commercial distributed hydrogen production system and incorporating knowledge gained from this demonstration project, we believe the hydrogen production rate can be increased with several improvements. A 40% increase in H₂ production will be possible when EGO induction control is improved to deliver nameplate coupled power (from the current ~21 kW to 30 kW total, or 5 kW per side of each SMR reactor). A further increase of up to 60% can be realized by switching to a higher power EGO induction system (changing from 5 kW to 8 kW per side of each SMR reactor). Another 60% increase can be obtained when the PSA skid is sized to match the reformer skid so that the H₂ recovery can achieve the PSA nameplate specification of 80% or greater. With the SMR reactor hardware identical to those installed in the demonstration pilot system, 100 kg-H₂/day production (i.e., 33 kg-H₂/day per SMR) may be achieved when all of the above improvements are made.

3.2 Hydrogen Product Purity

The purity of the hydrogen product gas from our demonstration pilot system has been verified to meet SAE J2719 standards by a reputable third-party laboratory specialized in impurity analysis of fuel cell grade hydrogen. The chosen test laboratory, SmartChemistry Corporation, located in Sacramento, California, has provided similar analytical support to SunLine in the past. The requested analysis for this project was for non-hydrogen contaminants (H_2O , O_2 , N_2 , CO_2 , Ar, He, NH_3), methane (CH_4), total hydrocarbon except for methane (C1 equivalent), carbonyl species (CO , HCHO , HCOOH), total sulfur compounds, halides (Cl_2 , HCl , HBr), and organic halides, etc. SmartChemistry's analytical methods ensure that the detection limits of these impurities are lower than the limits specified by SAE J2719 standards for hydrogen fuel.

We sampled the hydrogen product gas for the above offline analysis during both the shakedown testing and the extended operational test periods. A photo of the H_2 gas sampling setup is shown in Figure 7. In all cases, the analysis results showed that our hydrogen product gas meets the purity requirements per SAE J2719 standards. Results from the two rounds of sample analysis performed in June and December 2023 are presented in Figure 8 to Figure 12. Measured level of impurities are lower than SAE J2719 limits by a large margin. In early tests, the moisture level reported by offline analysis was slightly higher than the SAE J2719 standard limit. After determination that the erroneous readings were caused by insufficient purging of the sampling connection, a dewpoint sensor was installed on the hydrogen product sample line to ensure representative sampling. Subsequent offline analysis reported that the moisture level in the hydrogen gas was also lower than the SAE J2919 standard limit ($5 \mu\text{mol/mol}$).

Figure 7. Photo of hydrogen product sample collection for offline analysis by a third-party test lab.

Figure 8. Overview of STARS H₂ product analysis: non-H₂ impurity levels.

Figure 9. Overview of STARS H₂ product analysis: total sulfur impurity levels.

Figure 10. Overview of STARS H₂ product analysis: carbonyl impurity levels (total of carbon monoxide, formaldehyde, and formic acid).

Figure 11. Overview of STARS H₂ product analysis: methane impurity levels.

Figure 12. Overview of STARS H₂ product analysis: total hydrocarbon impurity levels (excluding methane).

3.3 Material and Energy Consumption

The Chemical Reaction Module, also known as the reformer skid, operated with a stable energy efficiency throughout the 24-month testing and operation period. Figure 13 shows the production rate in kg/day hydrogen in syngas as a function of the total induction power input to the SMR reactors. The production rate follows a very linear function with the electrical power, indicating that the electrical-to-chemical energy conversion occurred at a constant efficiency regardless of the reformer heat duty. The same function intercepts the x-axis at about 1 kW, which represents a fixed loss term that exists even if the reactors are kept at process temperature with zero feed flow. This remarkably low value of fixed loss indicates that the total heat loss through thermal insulation and joule heating of connection wiring has been very low.

Figure 13. Induction power consumption characteristics of the Chemical Reaction Module.

From process data collected over more than a cumulative 1000 hours of operation (Figure 14), the average natural gas consumption rate was 2.79 kg/kg-H₂. The average water consumption was 4.64 kg/kg-H₂. The large variations in feed rates in the early operation hours in Figure 14 were due to frequent adjustment of process control parameters while we tried to optimize control performance, including those for the water recycle loop. Thus, average feed consumption rates were calculated excluding these early data.

The above feed rate values are greater than the stoichiometric mass ratios of 2 and 4 for natural gas and water at full conversion, respectively. This is expected as the actual methane conversions were around 75%. Adjusted for the actual conversion, the natural gas and water consumption rates are close to the expected stoichiometric ratio. This result shows that the water recycling loop in our skid had performed very well.

The average induction power consumption at the SMR reactors was 9.65 kWh/kg-H₂. In the current pilot plant, steam generation was done by an electric boiler, which consumes roughly the same amount of electrical power as the induction heaters. In the next design for the commercial production system, energy for steam generation will be supplied primarily by heat recuperation within the process to eliminate the additional electricity demand. Considering utilities demand by other balance of plant equipment such as feed pumps, air compressors, process controllers, and the PSA system, the total electrical power consumption in the next commercial design is estimated to be around 15 kWh/kg-H₂, which includes roughly 10 kWh/kg-H₂ for inductive heating of the SMR reactors.

Figure 14. Feed material and induction power consumptions of the reformer skid during cumulative operation hours.

3.4 SMR Reactor Performance

To inform future improvements to the SMR reactor design, we benchmarked the current SMR reactors installed in the pilot plant Chemical Reaction Module. Process temperature, pressure, flow, and stream composition data were collected for an analysis of the energy balance around the SMR reactors. The boundary of the analysis includes the SMR reactors and the induction coils. Thus, the energy inputs to this subsystem are the electrical power transmitted to the induction coil and the chemical and physical enthalpies in the feed steam and natural gas stream. The energy output is the enthalpy of the syngas product stream from SMR reactors. The energy losses include heat loss from the reactors, resistive losses in the coil and power cables, and electromagnetic dissipation outside of the reactor receiving surfaces.

In our data analysis, the thermodynamic properties of the reactive streams were calculated independently by an in-house model tailored for rapid Excel data processing and by a model using commercial CHEMCAD process simulation software. The results agree with each other. The standard chemical exergy values are based on the Szargut model [5] with a reference environment selected at 25°C and 1 atm.

The SMR reactor energy efficiencies were evaluated by several related metrics, as defined in Section 2.3.2. Thermal energy efficiency, η_T , is defined as the reactive stream enthalpy increase divided by the electrical power into the induction coil. Electrical to chemical energy efficiency, or kWe-to-HHV efficiency, η_{HHV} , is defined as the higher heating value increase in the reactive stream divided by the induction power into the reactor. Exergy efficiency, η_{EX} , is defined in the conventional sense as the ratio of the total exergy coming out of the SMR reactors and the total exergy going into the reactors including the induction power.

The exergy efficiency of our SMR reactors was around 92%. This is higher than the performance of upper 80% achieved by prior work at PNNL under a different U.S. DOE project [4]. The higher efficiency is reasonable considering that in the current reactor design both sides of the SMR reactor are heated while the prior work was done with a single-side heated reactor where the unheated side allowed more heat loss. The current demo skid also operates at a significantly higher power and throughput than the previous work. Higher power operation at similar reactor temperatures tends to result in higher energy efficiency because the thermal loss term is relatively insensitive to the scale of power and process flow. The corresponding thermal energy efficiency of the SMR reactors was about 87%. The electrical to chemical energy (HHV) efficiency was about 95%.

A more rigorous analysis beyond the current work would require understanding of the uncertainties in the measured variables and propagating to an uncertainty in the estimated efficiencies. While most of the process measurements including temperature, pressure, mass flows, and syngas compositions have well defined accuracy values from manufacturer data, there are two gaps in the current setup. The natural gas flow control and meter is based on calibration to a specific standard composition (93% CH₄, 3% C₂H₆, 1% C₃H₈, 2% N₂, and 1% CO₂). Actual natural gas delivered to our skid onsite will have a different composition, which introduces a systemic bias that contributes to the uncertainty in natural gas component mass flows. The E.G.O. induction generators have onboard electronics that provide an actual induction power readout, but the signal's accuracy in the current version of hardware and firmware combination is undocumented. Therefore, it is desirable to define these remaining uncertainties in follow-on work so that future design improvements can be guided by good energy efficiency data.

The SMR methane conversions were about 75% under typical operation conditions (Table 3) such as those during the above benchmark testing. This level of methane conversion was expected for the relatively high pressure that the SMR reactors operated at because the SMR reaction is favored at low pressure. The moderate operating pressure was chosen because of the difficulty encountered, during the design and assembly phase, at procuring a syngas compressor during the COVID-19 pandemic that would have allowed the SMRs to operate at a low pressure. The approach to SMR equilibrium was estimated to be approximately 20°C, which is within the expected design margin. In the commercial design for distributed hydrogen production, substantially higher SMR conversions are possible through further flowsheet optimization.

Table 3. Typical SMR reactor conversions and approaches to reaction equilibrium¹

Reactor	Exit Temperature	Conversions (expressed in moles of CH ₄)		Approach to Equilibrium	
	T, °C	x ₁	x ₂	°C	%
SMR-D	775	0.751	0.432	20.8	93.8%
SMR-F	775	0.751	0.432	21.1	93.7%
SMR-E	755	0.751	0.432	1.2	99.8%

¹ Data based on test run 20240501 with assumed equal flow distribution among the three SMR reactors.

3.5 WGS Reactor Performance

The reformer unit used two fixed-bed WGS reactors arranged in sequential stages to convert more CO in syngas to H₂. The syngas product from SMR reactors typically contained about 12 mol% of CO₂ on a dry gas basis. Measured in the extent of WGS reaction on a feed methane basis, the shift conversion was about 43%, which is expected of the SMR reactors because the chemical equilibrium will allow some water gas shift reaction to occur even though the exothermic reaction is unfavored at the high temperature of SMR.

From the skid test results, the two-stage WGS reactors were able to convert additional CO to CO₂ and H₂. The WGS conversion, measured on feed methane basis, increased to 54% after the first stage of WGS. It increased further to 56% after the second stage. These conversions represent an approach to about 70% of the equilibrium conversions achievable at the WGS exit temperatures, typically 285°C to 290°C (Table 4). There was no sign of reverse WGS or methanation reactions taking place, as these side reactions would have caused the overall methane conversion to decrease, which was not observed.

Although the two-stage WGS included a water-cooled heat exchanger on the syngas stream between stages, we were not able to control the cooling water flow precisely due to an improperly sized control valve. As a result, the syngas stream passed through the intercooler without cooling in most of the skid test runs. The above WGS conversions were obtained in this flow configuration.

In the operation of our pilot plant, these WGS reactors performed satisfactorily. After reformer startup, the WGS reactors were able to maintain temperature and chemical conversion at steady state over extended operation periods. In the future designs, the intercooler between WGS stages can further improve overall shift conversions.

Table 4. Typical WGS reactor conversions and approaches to reaction equilibrium²

Reactor	Exit Temperature	Conversions (expressed in moles of CH ₄)		Approach to Equilibrium
	T, °C	x ₁	x ₂	%
WGS-1	290	0.753	0.544	74.5%
WGS-2	284	0.754	0.562	76.4%

3.6 System Reliability

By October 2024, we had achieved cumulative 1000 hours of pilot plant operation. A total of 1570 kg of hydrogen was produced by the reformer skid in the form of syngas. A total of 645 kg fuel cell grade hydrogen product was extracted by the PSA skid from the syngas stream. A total of 504 kg hydrogen was compressed and sent to SunLine facility for fueling its bus fleet.

At the SunLine H₂ fueling station attached to our pilot plant, an average of 72.4 kg hydrogen was dispensed for bus fueling daily. The pilot hydrogen production plant provided an average of 30 kg, or

² Data based on test run 20240501 with assumed equal flow distribution among the three SMR reactors.

41%, of the fueling demand at this station. This production rate represented about 16% of all hydrogen demand at SunLine at the time of the testing, including hydrogen supplied by SunLine’s own electrolyzer plant and a liquefied hydrogen facility.

After the initial shakedown and tuning tests, the integrated hydrogen production system operated reliably with only minor downtimes. In the last 520 hours of operation in 2024, the reformer and the PSA skids were able to maintain 96.5% uptime, while the downstream compression and storage system was active about 70% of the time. The downstream offtake was dictated mainly by SunLine bus fueling demand and schedule and did not reflect the performance of the hydrogen generator. The upstream production downtime totaled 23 hours, 62% of it occurring during production startups, 28% due to control program issues, and the remaining 10% due to utilities related upsets. The detailed breakdown is shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15. Breakdown of downtimes at the reformer and PSA skids during extended production operation.

The utilities related upsets were caused by the aging equipment such as the air compressor and the cooling tower struggling to maintain performance in the demanding hot desert climate at the Thousand Palms, California site. In future designs, these can be mostly eliminated with proper equipment sizing and maintenance programs. The reactor control related upsets were caused by minor data communication interface issues, which can be eliminated by corrections of program codes. These operational data show that high capacity factors can be achieved in the next design for a commercial distributed hydrogen production system.

4.0 Economic Analysis

4.1 Economic Summary

We anticipate that distributed hydrogen production using STARS Hydrogen Generators – located at, or near, California filling stations – will result in significant reductions in the “pump price” of hydrogen.

Drawing from our pilot plant experience, planned improvements for the first commercial STARS H₂ Generator, and recent policy developments, we project that first-year hydrogen production costs in California will be under \$6/kg. With increased numbers of H₂ Generators driving greater economies of hardware mass production, and through the additional development of advanced microchannel reactors and heat exchangers that yield higher efficiencies, we expect these costs to decrease to below \$5/kg in future years.

The 10-year subsidy provided by the Clean Hydrogen Production Tax Credit (IRS 45V) further reduces production costs by up to \$3/kg, if construction of the refueling stations begins before the end of 2027. The tax subsidy amount depends on variables including the lifecycle carbon emissions of methane feedstock and electricity.

Additional costs for compression, storage, and dispensing at filling stations are estimated at \$1.50–\$2.50 per kilogram. Combined, these costs and the tax credit yield a total “pump price” for distributed hydrogen in California ranging from about \$5/kg to \$8/kg. This is about \$30/kg less than the current hydrogen pump price at California stations.

This game changer can accelerate the adoption and mass production of hydrogen fuel cells and fuel cell vehicles, creating a “virtuous cycle” where increased demand for zero emission vehicles generates increased demand for hydrogen, fuel cells, and hydrogen generators, leading to greater economies of hardware mass production for each.

4.2 Economic Context and Background

STARS Technology Corporation was established in late 2016 to develop and commercialize advanced microchannel process technology for hydrogen production. The goal is to reliably produce hydrogen from natural gas and water, via the steam-methane reforming reaction, at or near the point of use and at affordable prices.

California has actively promoted alternative transportation fuels – including hydrogen. Despite the installation of numerous hydrogen filling stations, hydrogen prices at the pump, which in 2017 were \$15/kg (roughly equivalent to \$15 per gasoline gallon equivalent, or GGE), have increased to as much as \$36/kg in 2025 (Figure 16). The high cost of hydrogen has limited both market demand for hydrogen fuel cell vehicles (HFCVs) and the ability of automakers to transition to mass production, keeping fuel cell and component costs elevated.

Figure 16. Hydrogen priced at \$36/kg in 2025 at the dispenser of a hydrogen fuel station in California.

As of mid-2025, barriers still remain to achieving California’s goals. Efforts to increase clean hydrogen transportation have stalled because of limited availability and high cost of hydrogen. Even though hydrogen production from large-scale centralized, SMRs-processes can be produced at low cost, the expense of transporting hydrogen to refueling stations remains high – adding several dollars per kilogram. This high price has stifled the rollout of hydrogen fuel cell vehicles in California.

In contrast, clean carbon-negative compressed natural gas (CNG), produced from renewable natural gas and distributed through the natural gas grid, is available at more than 300 stations in California for under \$3 per GGE. The economics of the delivered RNG from the existing natural gas grid provide the energy needed to make affordable, clean hydrogen at a cost that is significantly below what is achievable using central hydrogen production with remote delivery as either compressed gas or liquefied hydrogen.

4.3 Tabular Economic Assessment for Distributed Hydrogen Production in California

This section presents a tabular comparison of hydrogen production costs for distributed STARS H₂ Generators (Table 5). The analysis assumes average California prices for industrial electricity and industrial natural gas, as reported by the U.S. Energy Information Administration. Costs include capital amortization as well as operations and maintenance. The actual production costs of hydrogen are sensitive to variability that exists in California depending on local utility rates at the distributed production site.

Table 5. Economic Breakdown of the Cost of Hydrogen Production.

	First Year At Low Levels of Hardware Mass Production	Levelized Cost Based on First Year Capital Costs	Nth Year At High Levels of Hardware Mass Production	Levelized Cost Based on Nth Year Capital Costs
Capital Cost	\$1.19/kg	\$1.19/kg	\$0.36/kg	\$0.36/kg
Electrical Cost	\$2.73/kg	\$3.15/kg	\$3.00/kg	\$3.46/kg
Methane Feedstock Cost	\$1.34/kg	\$1.54/kg	\$1.34/kg	\$1.54/kg
Other Operations and Maintenance	\$0.20/kg	\$0.23/kg	\$0.20/kg	\$0.23/kg
Sum of Production Cost Components	\$5.45/kg	\$6.11/kg	\$4.89/kg	\$5.58/kg
Potential Clean H2 Production Tax Credit	\$1.00-3.00/kg	\$1.00-3.00/kg	\$1.00-3.00/kg	\$1.00-3.00/kg
Net Production Cost after Clean H2 Production Tax Credit	\$2.45 – 4.45/kg	\$3.11 – 5.11/kg	\$1.89 – 3.89/kg	\$2.58 – 4.58/kg

Additional Notes:

- First-Year values reflect the initial higher hardware costs. Nth-Year values consider reduced hardware costs achieved, after “N” years, via increased volumes of hardware mass production and improved manufacturing processes.³
- Levelized costs are calculated using a 10% discount rate over 20 years.
- Clean Hydrogen Production Tax Credits are based on IRS 45V regulations and are shown as a range to reflect different scenarios for lifecycle carbon emissions and the use of combinations of renewable versus fossil natural gas.
- All costs are presented in 2025 dollars per kilogram of hydrogen (\$/kg H₂)
- Production costs and price at the pump are related but the price is sensitive to the amount of hydrogen being dispensed. The table cost values are based on 1500 kg/day dispensing rates.
- The table values do not include profit margins.
- General and administrative expenses and local utility rates vary significantly, which affect production costs.

³ Similar reductions in hardware costs were realized by Ford Motor Company during the first ten years of manufacturing the Ford Model T automobile.

5.0 Challenges and Mitigation

With any first-of-its-kind technology, there are challenges. When a new installation is placed into service, even with well-established technologies, there are lessons to be learned. One of the purposes of the H2 Silver STARS Project was to learn what we liked about the design and what we needed to improve on. The following section highlights the challenges and mitigations that have helped bring our hydrogen generator to Technology Readiness Level 7 (TRL-7).

The challenges included design concepts, construction errors, hardware limitations, and control algorithm shortcomings. As the project advanced each of these limitations were addressed so that by the end of the project the system was able to achieve high reliability as demonstrated by the greater than 95% system availability during the 300-hour continuous run and during the last six months of the demonstration.

The following discussion addresses “real world” conditions that impacted the steam methane reforming hydrogen generator operation at SunLine Transit Agency. The typical demonstration day at SunLine, until the last few weeks, including starting up in the morning and shutting down at the end of the day.

Daily operation of the demonstration plant was typically organized into the following steps: 1) system walking through to ensure the cooling tower, deionized water system, and air compressor were available, 2) startup sequencing, 3) heating the reactor to operating temperature of 750°C, 4) initiating syngas production, 5) bringing PSA online and venting product streams to atmosphere until ready to send to compression and storage, 6) monitoring hydrogen dewpoint sensor until moisture measurement is within specified value, 7) sending hydrogen to the compressor inlet tank, 8) ramping up the compressor to set hydrogen delivery pressure, 9) sending hydrogen to storage tank, 10) operating the system in steady state for as long as permitted, and 11) shutting down the system.

Many, but not all the elements of this process were followed over 120 times during the demonstration project as integration of the PSA and finally the compressor was accomplished. It was only in the last year of the project that the entire system integration was completed. Near the end of the project, 24-hour operating cycles began culminating in the 300-hour endurance run in October 2024. The following discussion provides insight into the challenges and mitigations that enabled the successful completion of the demonstration.

The ongoing and professional support provided by the SunLine team contributed greatly to the success of the project. They were instrumental in successfully integrating the compressor, maintaining the cooling tower, repairing the deionized water system, ensuring the availability of nitrogen, forming gas and specialty gases. Their ongoing support and encouragement were important contributions to the success of the demonstration project.

The lessons learned, experience gained, and production achieved during the commercial pilot demonstration are extremely valuable to the future of STARS Technology Corporation. We appreciate the leadership and sponsorship of both Southern California Gas Company and SunLine Transit Agency during the two-year commercial demonstration. We also appreciate the support provided by HiLine Engineering and Fabrication to fabricate the first-of-its-kind hydrogen generator.

5.1 Stability of Natural Gas and Electrical Mains

Natural Gas Supply – The pressure of the incoming natural gas supply line to the site was nearly always above 19 barg. This was a benefit to the operation of the hydrogen generator because it eliminated the need to have a compressor in the production process. However, on rare occasions, the natural gas pressure would drop below the operating pressure of process skid. When this occurred during operation, the system would sense low flow from the natural gas line and stop producing hydrogen.

Mitigation – In the commercial production design there will be a compressor added to ensure a constant flow of natural gas to the reactors. In addition, a regulator with sufficiently low pressure will be added to ensure that normal variations expected on the natural gas grid do not adversely affect the production of hydrogen.

Electrical Grid Transients – On one occasion during operation, there was an electrical grid transient that damaged many pieces of electrical equipment on site and caused a failure of one of the induction power supplies of the hydrogen generator.

Mitigation – The design of the electrical power system for the commercial hydrogen generator will include transient suppression protection.

5.2 Cooling Water Tower Operation

SunLine is in the Coachella Valley, a dry desert region of California. The open air forced draft cooling tower is supplied with deionized water. However, dust storms put fine silt into the water system. Filter medium was placed around the cooling tower intake to reduce the amount of silting. STARS installed a filter on the inlet of the cooling water to the process skid. It only took about 15 minutes to fully saturate the filter with debris in the water reducing the flow and pressure to the process skid. The cooling water filtration was abandoned afterwards. The pressure and flow of coolant to the reactor did not generally cause operational problems. However, after over a year of operations, STARS engineers serviced the intercooler and condensing heat exchangers by a cleaning-in-place method to improve thermal transfer. We managed to keep the microchannel heat exchangers from being clogged by debris at any time during all the tests.

Mitigation – The commercial version of the hydrogen generator will use pre-heating of natural gas and water to the hydrogen generator process to provide much of the cooling for the intercooler and condensing heat exchangers. A closed loop chiller will remove excess heat from the product stream. Induction heating will be used to supply additional heat to the steam methane feed mixture. This approach improves the efficiency of the process and eliminates the potential build-up of deposits and debris in the cooling system from the direct cooling tower approach used at SunLine.

5.3 Air Compressor Operation

The air compressor used during the project had been in storage after many years of operation prior to being used for the project. The system required periodic replacement of lubricant oil. During the project a temperature control component failed. A replacement part was not located.

Mitigation – STARS engineers disabled the temperature controlling component, which was designed to keep the system from operating when the conditions were too cold (not a problem in the Coachella Valley). Routine maintenance and replenishment and replacement of the oil kept the system operational through to the end of the project.

5.4 H₂ Purity Analysis

Once the process skid was working well, and the integration of the PSA was completed, samples of the hydrogen were sent out to an independent laboratory for analysis. The first two samples met the SAE-J2719 standard in everything except for moisture content.

Mitigation – After failing the second test because of moisture, a dewpoint sensor was added to the process control. This enabled direct reading of the moisture in the hydrogen stream from the PSA. The dewpoint sensor showed that moisture content in the system gradually decreased over a few hours until it was below the SAE-J2719 standard, which is 5 parts per million. In the two earlier tests, the system did not have adequate time to strip moisture out of the process and sample piping prior to taking the sample. The dewpoint sensor enabled STARS to monitor this important parameter. When the next sample was taken and in all subsequent times before sending hydrogen to the compressor, the dewpoint of the hydrogen was always below the required level.

5.5 Integration With Onsite H₂ Compression System

The integration with the onsite hydrogen compressor required connecting control circuitry between the compressor and hydrogen process skid. The challenge included ensuring adequate supply to the compressor, which has a recirculation loop that enabled us to operate the compressor at lower flow rates than optimal for the compressor. Occasional oil leaks within the compressor required maintenance, but the SunLine maintenance personnel were quickly able to restore operation of the compressor.

Mitigation – The process syngas flow transmitter from the CRM was sent out to be recalibrated for pure hydrogen flow measurement. The transmitter was then relocated to the suction section of the hydrogen compressor to provide a measure of the hydrogen from the PSA into the compressor.

5.6 Integration With Onsite Bus Fueling

While 500 kilograms of hydrogen were sent to SunLine's hydrogen storage tanks, SunLine's electrolyzer plant acceptance testing, which took several weeks, prevented us from sending more of the hydrogen that was produced to the buses. The moisture content measured during the first two samples also delayed sending the hydrogen to buses.

Mitigation – The addition of the dewpoint sensor provided the information needed to manage the sampling and monitor the hydrogen being sent to the buses. Hydrogen was discarded and vented when the tanks were not available to STARS during the electrolyzer acceptance testing. During October 2024 before completing the demonstration, we operated for a 300 continuous endurance hour run and supplied a substantial portion of the hydrogen SunLine used in its bus fleet.

6.0 Technology to Market

6.1 Overview of Adoption Readiness Assessment

As stated earlier, the H2 SilverSTARS project goal is to demonstrate that the distributed production of emissions-free renewable hydrogen for fuel cell vehicles (and other users) can achieve price competitiveness. Towards this goal, we have identified several key activities relevant to this technology demonstration project:

- (1) Demonstrate our pilot plant's ability to support fueling operation at SunLine Transit,
- (2) Demonstrate that the extended operation at a high-capacity factor in the actual environment of a fleet operator with a small staff, and
- (3) Obtain utility and raw material consumption data to support operating cost estimates of the STARS hydrogen generator.

Successful execution of these project activities has advanced our technology toward commercial applications. It is appropriate to evaluate the progress made under the current project in the context of the change in the adoption readiness of the technology being demonstrated. For this discussion, we have used the adoption readiness level (ARL) methodology proposed by U.S. DOE's Office of Technology Transition. Briefly, the ARL framework [6] assesses 17 dimensions grouped into four core readiness areas: Value Proposition, Market Acceptance, Resource Maturity, and License to Operate. By evaluating each readiness category, potential technology-to-market challenges and opportunities can be identified.

Inherent in such analysis is the time sensitivity to the current policy and business environments. For this report, we analyzed the ARL of STARS hydrogen generator technology at two state points: first at the beginning of the field demonstration in 2022, and again through the project end in October 2024 up to the present. Looking back to the inception of the project in 2020, the qualified value for adoption readiness level was much lower than in 2022 at the beginning of the field demonstration. The 2024 analysis uses EIA 2024 average cost of electricity and EIA 2024 average cost of methane. In the original DOE method, readiness in each category is evaluated as low, medium, or high. Before 2022 the readiness level of the hydrogen generator was clearly in the "low" range. As discussed below, the adoption readiness level of the STARS Hydrogen Generator has been elevated to the "high" range both because of activities directly related to the successful completion of the SilverSTARS demonstration and because of market and policy changes that favor market entry.

For the period of 2022 through the present, we modified the readiness rating by assigning numerical values of readiness between 1-9 to capture better the readiness gradient. Thus, a value 0-3 corresponds to a lower readiness level, 4-6 to medium, and 7-9 to high. Detailed descriptions of the DOE ARL criteria are provided in Appendix A.

6.2 Project Impact on Adoption Readiness

The readiness evaluation scores of all categories considered in the ARL assessment are tabulated below.

Table 6. STARS Distributed Hydrogen Generator – ARL assessment results (1 low readiness, 9 high readiness).

RISK CATEGORY	YEAR 2022	YEAR 2025	CHANGE
VALUE PROPOSITION			
Delivered Cost	5	7	2
Functional Performance	6	8	2
Ease of Use	4	8	4
MARKET ACCEPTANCE			
Demand Maturity / Market Openness	7	9	2
Market Size	5	9	4
Downstream Value Chain	5	7	2
RESOURCE MATURITY			
Capital Flow	5	7	2
Project Development, Integration, & Management	4	7	3
Infrastructure	6	8	0
Manufacturing & Supply Chain	6	8	2
Materials Sourcing	8	8	0
Workforce	6	9	3
LICENSE TO OPERATE			
Regulatory Environment	5	7	2
Policy Environment	3	7	4
Permitting & Siting	4	8	4
Environmental & Safety	9	9	0
Community Perceptions	8	8	0
OVERALL AVERAGE	5.4	7.4	2.4

The market conditions needed for the successful entry of STARS’ distributed hydrogen generators have greatly improved. The H2 SilverSTARS project activities and industry outreach efforts have been augmented by external conditions including the passage of the Big Beautiful Bill, which provides statutory certainty for qualification to receive the Clean Hydrogen Production Tax Credit (allowed by the Internal Revenue Service’s 45V). The 45V tax credit provides a substantial incentive to start clean hydrogen projects prior to the end of 2027.

Federal policies have undergone significant change under the new administration. Some of these policies such as the application of tariffs, and the time frame reduction in the applicability of the Inflation

Reduction Act (IRA) incentives can have both helpful and harmful effects on the commercialization efforts. As shown in Table 6, we believe that although there are challenges created by these policies, overall, we are better off because of the inherent strengths of our business plan.

Our conclusion is that our technology is more mature, and the policy and regulatory environments are better than they were in 2022. As a result, the overall adoption readiness is now significantly higher at the successful conclusion of the H2 SilverSTARS demonstration project.

As shown in Figure 17, significant improvements were made to both the technology and adoption readiness levels. This improvement is important because it is a measure of the success of the project, which is also a measure of the benefits to SoCalGas ratepayers. The improvement in readiness also helps to reduce the time to market for this disruptive technology.

Figure 17. Advancement of Technology and Adoption Readiness Levels of STARS distributed hydrogen generator technology.

6.3 ARL Assessment – Value Proposition

6.3.1 Delivered Cost

The DOE method defines readiness in deliver cost as those “*associated with achieving delivered cost competitiveness when produced at full scale, including amortization of incurred development and capital costs, and accounting for switching costs (if any).*”

In the context of the market for distributed hydrogen production technologies, we define “full scale” to mean that the hydrogen generating systems are manufactured with the economics of hardware mass production and that the production environment is equipped with centralized monitoring and operational support for the system. Further, “delivered cost” includes two primary components, i.e., capital expenditures (CapEx) and operational expenditures (OpEx). A third component, which is not included in this evaluation, is the availability of incentives and grants. The analysis does not include the downstream costs of compression, storage and dispensing of hydrogen.

For the first commercial product, as discussed in Table 5, Section 4.3, we project a first year production cost of \$5.45/kg H₂, which is significantly lower than SunLine’s cost for liquid hydrogen delivery and/or the hydrogen produced by their electrolyzer. Before demonstrating the reliability and operating cost of the STARS hydrogen generator the adoption readiness was evaluated to be a value of 5. This score is in the middle of the medium readiness category. Based on the analysis below, we assigned a readiness level value of 7 to the delivered cost for STARS Distributed SMR Hydrogen Generation.

During this project, the technology had been tested with over 120 cold start operating cycles. The system had operated for a total of over 1,000 hours at SunLine. The last 6 months of the demonstration included many hours of delivering hydrogen to the SunLine buses. The demonstration de-risked the new technology. The 300-hour endurance run demonstrated that the system could run continuously under its automated controls and deliver hydrogen to the buses. These factors are immediate justification for raising the value of the production design, which incorporates lessons learned from the demonstration.

Further, also in Table 5, Section 4.3, we estimate that the first year “pump price” will be in the range of \$5 to \$8 per kilogram, with the range depending on the amount of the Clean Hydrogen Production Tax Credit is earned and the cost of downstream operations at the filling station (compressing, storing, dispensing, etc). The added efficiency of light duty fuel cell vehicles results in fuel cost per mile of about 7.7 – 12.3¢ per mile, based on 65 miles per kg H₂. This compares very favorably to a cost of 15¢ per mile for a light duty gasoline powered vehicle that gets 30 miles per gallon, based on \$4.50 per gallon. The adoption cost readiness of the STARS hydrogen generator will continue to improve during the development of the production unit’s manufacturing and design, and because of future cost benefits from hardware mass production.

The STARS cost of hydrogen is a clear advantage over other hydrogen sources and can compete against gasoline powered vehicles.

6.3.2 Functional Performance

The DOE method defines readiness in achieving functional performance to be associated “*with the ability of the technology solution to meet or exceed the performance and feature-set of incumbent solutions or create new end-use markets.*” The ultimate functionality is to provide affordable hydrogen with a low carbon intensity. We assign a readiness value of 6 in providing functional performance in 2022 prior to this project and have increased the readiness value of 8 in 2025 after the project.

The strengths of the project include: 1) Inductively heating the reactor. This was a major deviation from traditional steam methane reforming that reduced the carbon intensity by 30% compared to traditional steam methane reforming technology. 2) Using RNG to produce hydrogen. This enabled the system to supply renewable hydrogen to the buses and allows the hydrogen product to meet the definition of Clean Hydrogen in the Bipartisan Infrastructure Act (PL 117.58). 3) Producing hydrogen onsite eliminated the costs of transporting hydrogen from production sites to SunLine. The largest single element of cost for hydrogen is the cost to deliver the hydrogen offsite. 4) Cost avoidance by using existing natural gas infrastructure. The capital cost of the infrastructure needed to deliver hydrogen onsite is greatly reduced by eliminating the need to transport hydrogen. 5) Using RNG to make hydrogen creates new jobs and industry by converting organic waste streams into product streams. This is a community benefit that provides good job opportunities and new revenue streams to rural areas of the country. 6) The ability to produce carbon negative hydrogen. The “Book and Claim” process allows hydrogen producers to use renewable natural gas with a carbon negative GREET as documented by the California Air Resources Board. 7) Lower electrical energy demand. The STARS hydrogen generating system uses about 1/4 the electrical energy of electrolyzers to directly produce hydrogen from water. This reduces the need for new electrical infrastructure.

There are two lessons learned that will improve functional performance: 1) Eliminate the use of a cooling tower through improved thermal recuperation from the process. Cooling towers are a traditional approach but during the pilot demonstration the cooling tower reduced efficiency and therefore increased the cost of hydrogen. 2) Replace the electric steam boiler with better heat recovery and localized heating of the process. The electric boiler that was used for the demonstration will not be used in the commercial production unit.

The functionality of the commercial system is improved because: 1) The commercial design maximizes recuperation of waste heat used to produce steam and preheat the steam-methane reactant mix. This provides a 25% reduction in total electrical power compared to the 2022 design. 2) Improved recuperative heat exchange and the inclusion of a small chiller replaces the cooling tower and substantially reduces the amount of waste heat. The chiller also reduces the footprint of the process and eliminates potential fouling of microchannel heat exchangers. 3) Automated control functions were improved. Autonomous operations with remote monitoring and central support staff reduce the cost of hydrogen while gaining the economics of scale by using a central support infrastructure to manage multiple regional locations.

6.3.3 Ease of Use / Complexity

The DOE method defines readiness in usability and complexity in terms of “*operational switching costs; the ability of a new user (individual, company, system integrator) to adopt and operationalize the technology with limited training, few new requirements, or special resources (e.g., tools, workforce,*

contract structures)." We assign a value of 4 at the start of the project in 2022, and a value of 8 in 2025 at the completion of the project.

The demonstration system was designed to operate autonomously through each of its program functions: system pressure test, reduction of catalyst, heat up, and production. The system also required no operator interaction for normal or emergency shutdowns. At SunLine, some of the valves on the skid needed to be prepositioned to allow operation. In addition, the cooling tower, instrument air system, deionized water, pressure swing adsorber, and compressor systems needed to be manually placed into service. This reduced the ability to fully automate the process during the demonstration. However, the operation of each of these systems is not difficult for an energy system trained operator. When the sequence was on hold awaiting the completion of an interlock or when the system automatically took a control action to respond to an off normal situation, it was often challenging to determine the initiating cause of the action.

The commercial design will incorporate lessons learned from the demonstration including providing more operator aids in the human machine interface (HMI). This includes an HMI page that provides the operator with the parameter value and setpoint that must be achieved that is delaying completion of the interlock required to progress to the next step in the operating sequence. In addition, the control system will identify the parameter that causes an unplanned control function. Finally, a digital twin of the process will provide simulated operating experience and support remote troubleshooting which will enhance operability. These enhancements will save operators hours of troubleshooting and trying to understand why the system took the action taken.

6.4 ARL Assessment – Market Acceptance

6.4.1 Demand Maturity / Market Openness

The DOE method defines readiness in this category in terms of “*demand certainty and access to standardized sales & contracting mechanisms (if required), as well with natural (e.g., network effects, first-mover-advantages) and / or structural (e.g., existing monopolies / oligopolies) barriers to entry in the market(s) to which the technology solution can be applied.*” We assign a readiness value of 7 at the beginning of the project progressing to 8 by the end of the project.

Fleet operators, and other hydrogen users require a high degree of certainty that they will have the hydrogen needed for their enterprise. In many cases in California, the delivery of hydrogen has not been reliable. The distributed, onsite placement of the STARS hydrogen generator enables the end user to control the energy they need to carry out their functions. The addition of properly sufficient onsite storage provides necessary time for the response to unplanned system outages. The STARS modular design enables hardware mass production of the hydrogen syngas generating components. The demonstration system could be operated with either 1, 2 or all 3 reactors. This redundancy makes it possible to take one or more of the reactors out of service to conduct maintenance without shutting down the entire system. The use of RNG provides hydrogen users with a carbon neutral to carbon negative resource that will qualify for the Inflation Reduction Act (IRA) (PL 117-169) \$3 dollar per kilogram Clean Hydrogen Production tax credit (IRS 45V). The economic and environmental benefits of the STARS system are attractive to end users. The approach has received special recognition at the Rice Alliance Venture

Conferences, the Canadian Hydrogen Convention Awards, and Darcy Partner's ten most innovative technologies.

STARS is developing partnership agreements with hydrogen industry companies that integrate technologies for hydrogen fueling stations and other users. These companies have major oil and gas company customers that use their services. STARS and Total Hydrogen Services have submitted a joint proposal to a request for proposal (RFP) from First Public Hydrogen Authority. In addition, STARS and FASTECH have recently signed a memorandum of agreement to work jointly on developing a mobile refueling capability. STARS also has signed a memorandum of agreement with Sugar Valley Energy for the potential delivery of up to 40 of the 1500 kg per day systems.

STARS hydrogen generating technology provides affordable, low-carbon hydrogen in an operational configuration that will fit in many commercial and industrial locations. The commercial design provides up to 1500 kg/day of hydrogen by installing six 250 kg/day Chemical Reaction Modules. Each module operates autonomously. The use of control and power connectors enable rapid replacement of a failed reaction module. It will be possible to do routine maintenance on a rotating basis so that production can achieve greater than 90% availability.

6.4.2 Market Size

The DOE method defines market size readiness to be “*the overall size of the market that can be served by the technology, and the level of uncertainty with which it will materialize.*” We assign a value of 5 to this readiness level in 2022 but the market has matured and the level of interest in transitioning fleets to hydrogen has greatly improved. We assign a value of 9 to the market readiness of the STARS hydrogen generator.

The future growth of hydrogen market has much uncertainty; however, independent analysts project that the market for hydrogen may grow between 5 and 8-fold by 2050. The niche for distributed hydrogen lies between one-third and two-thirds of the predicted growth. The modular design and modest 1500 kg/day production has a competitive advantage because it can populate transportation routes within 5 years while the larger central hubs will take much longer to license, finance, construct, and place into service.

STARS' business model is based on distributed hydrogen generation at the point of use or sale using the economics of hardware mass production to drive down the capital cost of the system, and to use the economics of scale from central monitoring and control via the internet to drive the maintenance and operating costs of the hydrogen down. A distributed network of onsite hydrogen generators can fill the gap between major hydrogen generating hubs. The relatively small size of the 1500 kg/day distributed hydrogen generator systems also enable them to scale up by numbering up to meet expanding demand as the hydrogen energy economy develops. Industry interest and opportunities are continuing to grow as both STARS' experience from conducting the demonstration has grown and also as the market is maturing.

6.4.3 Downstream Value Chain

The DOE method defines Downstream Value Chain Readiness as being “*the projected path to get the product from a producer to a customer along the value chain (e.g., considering split incentives, technology acceptance, business model changes).*” We assign a value of 5 to this readiness level in 2022. Increasing market and value chain development has improved the readiness value to 7 in 2025.

At the start of the demonstration project, STARS was focused on being an original equipment manufacturer of microchannel devices that can make hydrogen. During the development of the project and after participating in several industry Expos, STARS added the complete hydrogen syngas Chemical Reaction Module to its product line. This was because downstream developers, including EPCs and integrators, did not understand how to use our hardware in their designs. It was incumbent on us to demonstrate how the modular design could facilitate low-cost hydrogen. A strength of the STARS’ approach is non-reliance on government subsidies or grants to produce economically viable hydrogen. STARS has entered memoranda of agreement with several technology integrating companies where each organization gains value by being associated with the others.

6.5 ARL Assessment – Resource Maturity

6.5.1 Capital Flow

The DOE method defines Capital Flow Readiness in terms of “*the availability of capital needed to move the technology solution from its current state to production at scale, including total investment required, availability of willing investors, availability of associated financial & insurance products, and the speed of capital flow.*”

We assign a value of 5 to this readiness level in 2020, when SoCalGas contracted with STARS to produce a commercial prototype hydrogen generator using STARS’ patented microchannel devices. The contract provided \$1.7 million dollars to design, fabricate, purchase and operate the prototype at SunLine transit. These funds provided adequate support when augmented by STARS’ friends and family investors and a local angel investment group. In 2025, the environment for raising additional capital improved greatly. We assign a value of 7 to the capital flow readiness level.

The H2 SilverSTARS project success demonstrates the hydrogen generator’s reliability, efficiency, and approach to delivering onsite hydrogen to end users. The results provide concrete evidence of how STARS distributed hydrogen production provides value to customers and support our efforts to raise the capital needed to continue with the last step of commercialization. In the interim, until new financing is secured, development of the commercial prototype is limited to conserve resources.

Our funding activities include contracting with fund-raising organizations to identify potential investors, development of consortia that can generate sales of the microchannel devices, and support submission of responses to proposals. Activities include working with a freelance business development person on a commission only basis. Success in any of these activities will accelerate the commercial development and availability of STARS hydrogen generating components.

6.5.2 Project Development, Integration, and Management

The DOE method defines project development, integration and management readiness as “*the existence of processes and capabilities to successfully and repeatably execute projects using the technology solution.*” We assign a relatively low readiness value of 4 in 2020 at the project start. The development of consortia and teaming arrangements with other industry partners has greatly improved our ability to carry development and operation of hydrogen refueling infrastructure leading us to conclude that in 2025 our readiness value is a 7.

In 2022, STARS was focused on fabrication of the hardware with HiLine Engineering and Fabrication, a boutique firm in Richland WA. HiLine has special expertise supporting the nuclear industry and food processing industry. They also provide ongoing support to DOE’s Hanford Cleanup Project. STARS hired Barr Engineering to help to develop the initial hydrogen generator design. Eventually Barr supported SoCalGas as their independent engineering organization. Burns McDonnell Engineering supervised site construction. The coordination of these companies was jointly managed by STARS and SoCalGas.

Recently, STARS has begun discussions with two experienced companies that have expertise in the design, construction and operation of hydrogen fueling stations. One of the companies, Total Hydrogen Services is part of a STARS led consortium that proposed to supply hydrogen to the First Public Hydrogen Authority. With the experiences gained in the now completed demonstration project and with the recent development of team partners for future projects, we believe that STARS has a strong base of support for project development, planning, and execution.

6.5.3 Infrastructure

The DOE method defines infrastructure readiness as “*the physical and digital large-scale systems that need to be in place to support, enable, or facilitate deployment at full scale (e.g., pipelines, V transmission lines, roads and bridges, etc.)*.” We assign a readiness value of 6 in 2022 that has progressed to a readiness value of 8 in 2025.

The initial hydrogen generator design provided 4 discrete components that needed to be installed on site. The interconnection of these components required trenching and laying of piping and conduit below grade. It also required extensive electrician and pipefitter hours to complete the interconnection. The layout increased the footprint needed to install the hardware. Provisions were made for remote operation of the system.

During the demonstration project, the Allen Bradley control system was operated remotely using a industrial-strength secure cloud to support activities that required the onsite person to be away from the system during the 24/7 continuous operations activities.

The repurposing of the natural gas infrastructure using STARS H₂ Generators and RNG provides a low-cost approach to the rollout of hydrogen infrastructure. The balancing of capacity and need that is provided by the STARS modular approach minimizes time to implementation and financial risk.

STARS has been working with Honeywell controls engineers to develop a conceptual design of the digital support needed to control multiple distributed hydrogen systems remotely. Minimal infrastructure is needed to implement the STARS business model.

6.5.4 Manufacturing & Supply Chain

The DOE method defines adoption readiness as “*all the entities & processes that will produce the end-product, including integrators, component and sub-component manufacturers & providers.*” We assign a relatively high readiness level of 6 in 2022 that has progressed to an 8 in 2025.

The demonstration project design uses “off the shelf” components including the induction generators. The additively manufactured components can be produced by any competent metal printing company. There are many options available for RNG. Book and Claim policies create a competitive marketplace and enable rural communities to participate in the energy transition. The commercial production hydrogen generator design continues to follow these principles, and the modular design of the Chemical Reaction Modules enables hardware mass production techniques that will reduce costs and provide high reliability to customers.

6.5.5 Materials Sourcing

The DOE method defines adoption readiness as “*the availability of critical materials required by the technology (e.g., rare earth and other limited availability materials).*” We assign a relatively high and unchanged readiness value of 8 in 2022 and 2025, as all materials and processes needed to manufacture the hydrogen generator were available from a competitive and distributed marketplace. In 2025 impacts of tariffs on some products from Canada, Germany and China are unknown but may impact material choices.

6.5.6 Workforce

The DOE method defines adoption readiness as “*the human capital and capabilities required to design, produce, install, maintain, and operate the technology solution at scale.*” We assign a value of 6 in 2022 prior to this project, with improvement to 9 in 2025 after the project.

The pilot plant’s automated sequencing of the process reduces but does not eliminate the need for competent operators and maintainers. In the commercial design, the operability of the STARS hydrogen generator is much improved. Multiple identical Chemical Reaction Modules, improvements to control algorithms, ability to incorporate artificial intelligence (AI) into the control scheme, and development of a digital twin all enhance a qualified energy operators’ rapid qualification on the hardware.

6.6 ARL Assessment – License to Operate

6.6.1 Regulatory Environment

The DOE method defines adoption readiness as the “*local, state, and federal regulations or other requirements / standards that must be met to deploy the technology at scale.*” We assign a moderate value of 5 in 2022 progressing to 8 in 2025.

The ASME Boiler and Pressure Vessel Code does not recognize additive manufacturing as an acceptable means of constructing a pressure vessel. However, in California and Washington State, and other states, ASME code exceptions exist for small vessels that operate under 250 PSI and have an internal volume of less than 5 cubic feet. Discussions with the California Chief Inspector’s Office have led to a process for demonstrating the integrity of the pressure vessels using ASME, UG-99 pressure testing protocols. The current readiness level would be higher except for the time and effort it may take to gain regulatory approval for the hydrogen generator in states where there is no exclusion. This does not greatly restrict the rapid deployment but will require extra effort before the hardware can be deployed within the states that do not have exemptions. However, technical acceptance is probable because of the small internal volume of the reactor and recuperating heat exchanger, which are approximately 500 milliliters total volume. HiLine Engineering and Fabrication are certified to construct UL approved hardware and have an exceptional workforce and quality assurance program. STARS is working with HiLine Engineering to develop the modular design of hydrogen production system. Although there may be some challenges in getting regulatory approval, there is no valid technical reason not to approve its use.

6.6.2 Policy Environment

The DOE method defines adoption readiness as “*local, state, and federal government policy actions that support or hinder the adoption of the technology at scale.*” We assign a relatively low value of 3 in 2022 at the project start but have seen improvements that provide a readiness value of 7 in 2025.

STARS’ business model has always been focused on reducing the cost of hydrogen production to compete with gasoline and diesel as transportation fuel. The federal incentives add value but are not essential to STARS’ success. Public Law 119-21, also commonly referred to as “The Big Beautiful Bill”, retained qualification for the Inflation Reduction Act, 45V tax credits until the end of 2027. By creating a limited window, the policy adds incentive to users that are planning to transition their fleets to clean hydrogen. This has created a thirty-month window of opportunity. The rapid project development and limited risk associated with distributed projects provide STARS with a competitive advantage over central production facilities that will take a much longer timeframe. It will be difficult for the large central plants to begin construction before the end of 2027. However, it may free-up investment speculation to reduce the financial risk by producing hydrogen that qualifies for the 45V tax credits. Our rapid response capabilities, low intrinsic price of hydrogen to refueling stations, and the problems that have plagued California’s ambitious goals for deploying clean transportation fuels, provides us an opportunity to help ARCHES achieve their goals.

The readiness value could be increased to a readiness value of 9 if California policies would encourage not only private industry but also allow regulated utilities to use distributed hydrogen

production approaches, like STARS' to rapidly deploy low-cost, low-carbon hydrogen for transportation and other purposes. The use of the natural gas grid to support clean hydrogen production repurposes and maintains the value of pipeline infrastructure for natural gas utilities. The potential to use hydrogen as an energy storage source for the electrical grid and as a potential future microgrid energy source would also avoid some electrical energy infrastructure costs. Regulated utilities were used in the early development of the national electrical grid and provided the base opportunity for the use of Renewable Natural Gas at Compressed Natural Gas filling stations.

California's long-standing commitment to developing clean energy for transportation establishes California as an important market for STARS. Successful deployment of hydrogen generators in California will open doors to other states.

6.6.3 Permitting & Siting

The DOE method defines adoption readiness as “*the process to secure approvals to site and build equipment & infrastructure associated with deploying the technology at scale.*” We assign a relatively low value of 4 in California in 2022 that has improved to an 8 in 2025.

It took many months to obtain permits for the demonstration project. SoCalGas Company has highly capable experts in licensing and permitting. Part of the challenge of obtaining licenses and permits for the STARS design is that the technology is not well understood, and the regulations were developed to license large central production designs. The small internal volume and the reduction in carbon and nitrogen oxide emissions from the inductively heated reactor greatly reduces the source term for both safety and the environment. Discussions with Washington State and California inspectors have helped to clear the path for permitting and licensing.

It is anticipated that licensing the first commercial production system will take several months because the technology and distributed approach are new. Regulatory organizations will need to fully consider the potential impacts of distributed systems. This requires new interpretations of standards and regulations. However, licenses and permits for subsequent, distributed hydrogen generators will require less time once the precedent is established by the initial licenses and permits. The modular “cookie cutter” approach has the potential to streamline licensing and permitting. Future regulatory and permit approvals will need to address the specifics of the local jurisdiction, but the underlying technology safety and environmental compliance will be established after the first few installations.

6.6.4 Environmental & Safety

The DOE method defines adoption risks in this category as those associated with “*the potential for hazardous side effects or adverse events inherent to the production, transport, or use of the technology solution or end product in the absence of sufficient controls.*” We assign a high readiness value of 9 to this readiness level, which is unchanged from 2022 to 2025.

There are two attributes that reduce emissions in the STARS hydrogen generator. The first is the use of induction heating of the endothermic reaction. By substituting electrical heating in place of burning natural gas, there is a 30% reduction in carbon emissions compared to conventional SMRs. There is also a 100% reduction in produced SO_x and NO_x because there are no flue gas emissions. The second attribute

is the use of RNG in place of fossil fuel. This allows SMR production that is carbon neutral or carbon negative depending on the carbon intensity of the RNG.

In terms of safety, hydrogen, like natural gas is a hazardous energy if not properly managed. Hydrogen fires can occur when the hydrogen and air mixture is between 4% and 75% by volume. Explosive detonation can occur between 18% and 59% by volume. The STARS hydrogen generator has several engineered features to prevent mishaps.

Microchannel reactors used in the STARS hydrogen Generator have 1/100th the volume of conventional SMRs. This reduction in volume reduces the source-term energy that can result in a fire or explosion. The small exterior volume of the reactor and high temperature heat exchanger is about 500 milliliters, or about 2 cups. The even smaller internal volume enables rapid purging with nitrogen in the event a leak or fire is detected. Sensors include natural gas and hydrogen which initiate an emergency shutdown if either gas is detected above its safe threshold. A backup infrared flame detector provides redundant protection against conflagration. The air inside the process skid is changed multiple times per minute by forced air fans in the side of the skid. Together, these engineered safety features control the risk of fire or detonation.

Hydrogen production using microchannel reactors is scaled up by increasing the number of reactors rather than by making the reactors larger. This design feature limits the inherent risk from auto-ignition of the process to leakage from a single reactor. The downstream environmental and safety of the process is unchanged from that of conventional hydrogen processes.

6.6.5 Community Perception

The DOE method defines Community Perception readiness “*the general perception by global and local communities of the technology solution and its risks or impact, whether founded or unfounded.*” We assign a readiness value of 8 that is unchanged from 2022 to 2025.

Distributed hydrogen production systems limit risk to the public. The STARS system does not generate nuisance noise, SO_x, or NO_x. The system will normally be installed in protected areas of the facility where hydrogen is needed. Installation does not involve disruptions to traffic such as would be likely with pipeline distribution of hydrogen. The use of renewable natural gas further aligns with public desire to have cleaner and sustainable energy sources.

The reaction of the community during the unveiling ceremony at SunLine supports the contention that the STARS hydrogen generator will continue to receive favorable public acceptance. The deployment of the STARS distributed hydrogen generators creates new jobs in agriculture, food processing, and waste management by creating demand for RNG. The use of hydrogen creates high paying jobs in transportation, industry, and energy sectors. Distributed production provides access to clean energy even in rural and underserved communities. Affordable and clean hydrogen is clearly a public benefit.

7.0 References

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Appendix A Adoption Readiness Assessment Criteria (U.S. Department of Energy)

A.1 Value Proposition

Risk Category	Readiness Value		
	High (7-9)	Medium (4-6)	Low (1-3)
Delivered Cost	Technology solution is either: (a) currently more cost effective than the incumbent or competing technology, or (b) close to cost-parity and on a clear cost curve to achieve cost parity within 3 years, and fundamental cost components (e.g., cost of critical inputs) are not at risk of significant market swings.	Technology solution is more than 3 years away from achieving cost parity with incumbent or competing technology but is on a clear path to be more cost effective; and / or there are some fundamental cost components that are at risk of market swings.	Technology solution is more expensive than the incumbent or competing in technology and there is no clear pathway to cost competitiveness without substantial additional R&D advances.
Functional Performance	Technology solution provides sustained improved performance and / or benefits that justify a premium (if any) in an existing end-use case or value in a new end-use case.	Technology solution provides equivalent functionality to existing products (i.e., same performance on all key parameters), or improved performance does not justify current premium, or performance differential will not be sufficiently sustained (e.g., lack of fundamental competitive advantage or weak IP protection allows incumbent or competitors to reduce differential quickly).	Technology solution provides poorer functionality than existing solutions currently in place.
Ease of Use / Complexity	Technology solution is easy to use / operate & maintain by the typical user / operator (e.g., highly intuitive with little need for additional training or similar to existing systems) and is plug-and-play with current infrastructure / equipment.	Technology solution can be operated & maintained by a typical user / operator after some training and allows for interoperability with existing infrastructure / equipment with minor adjustments.	Technology solution deployment requires extensive operations and maintenance training of personnel and / or there are meaningful integration costs to successfully use / integrate the product.

A.2 Market Acceptance

Risk Category	Readiness Value		
	High (7-9)	Medium (4-6)	Low (1-3)
Demand Maturity / Market Openness	There is a clear pathway for the technology solution to be introduced in a target market and gain initial traction; and there is standardized off-take (e.g., long-term agreements, hedge-able commodity market, accessible consumer market).	Technology solution would need to overcome substantial barriers to entry from competing technologies to enter the market but has a clear pathway to do so; and there is a developing standardization of offtake.	Technology solution's ability to enter the market is limited due to incumbent advantages and market barriers to entry; or off-take is not easy / standardized and does not meet the needs of technology solution deployment.
Market Size	Technology solution is well positioned to compete strongly in a large and existing market or dominate market share in a small and existing market; technology solution can be broadly adopted across geographies.	Technology solution addresses only a moderately sized existing market opportunity, and / or there is moderate uncertainty to whether the market will materialize; technology solution may be limited to select markets because of geographic or other constraints.	Technology solution is limited to small markets, and / or relies on a market that has yet to materialize.
Downstream Value Chain	Path to market is clear; business proposition and technology solution features work within existing incentives / business models, or newly aligns incentives for stakeholders along the value chain	Path to market requires realigning of value chain; business model and technology acceptance level are not clear for one or more participants in current value chain.	Value chain is non-existent, highly fragmented, and / or technology solution benefits do not accrue to critical decision makers / gate keepers across value chain.

A.3 Resource Maturity

Risk Category	Readiness Value		
	High (7-9)	Medium (4-6)	Low (1-3)
Capital Flow	Institutional investors confirm return profile in this technology solution is commercially competitive with their broader portfolio. Deal flow / risk profile is sufficient to develop regular equity & debt approval processes at relevant investment institutions & ratings agencies. Major risks are insurable.	There exist one or more “valleys of death” along the required capital stack to full deployment, but hurdles can be overcome, and capital flow & financial and insurance availability is beginning to increase.	Significant additional investment from sources of concessionary / patient / high risk pools of capital (e.g., public sector, philanthropic, and catalytic venture capital) required to achieve deployment.
Project Development, Integration, and Management	Mature processes and capabilities exist (e.g., within EPC contractors) to develop, integrate, and manage full projects using the technology solution; demonstrated by a track record of on-budget, on-time projects using the technology solution or comparable projects.	Some processes and capabilities exist to develop, integrate, and manage full projects using the technology solution; but these are as-yet unproven.	Deployment of the technology solution requires building new or significantly improved project development, integration, and management processes and capabilities as compared with the industry status quo; demonstrations and deployments at scale face substantial budget and timeline risks as a result.
Infrastructure	Technology solution can be broadly deployed within existing large-scale physical and digital infrastructure.	Technology solution can be broadly deployed with minimal investment in large-scale infrastructure (i.e., existing infrastructure can be adapted to use with new technology solution) or there exists a clear and economic pathway for investors & developers to build required infrastructure.	Technology solution can be broadly deployed only with additional significant investments in new largescale infrastructure and pathway to required infrastructure remains unclear.
Manufacturing & Supply Chain	Technology solution deployment relies on off-the-shelf or simple adaptation of existing supply base products & existing manufacturing capabilities.	Technology solution deployment requires new components or products that are aligned with existing supply base capabilities but that may require minor upgrades or retooling of manufacturing and other processes.	Technology solution deployment requires creation of new manufacturing processes or supply chain components that are not currently in place, or deployment will overwhelm existing supply chain capacities.

(Continued)

Risk Category	Readiness Value		
	High (7-9)	Medium (4-6)	Low (1-3)
Material Sourcing	Technology solution relies on materials that are readily available in a competitive and distributed market and can be procured off the shelf with little to no geopolitical risk.	Technology solution relies on materials that are abundantly available but may face some risks (e.g., rely on new processing methods to make suitable for the application, geographic concentration).	Technology solution relies on materials that are limited in supply relative to the needed demand, may be difficult to obtain, may face geopolitical risks, or are very costly to produce in the needed quantities.
Work Force	Existing workforce has the necessary skills to manufacture and deploy technology solution with little additional training or significant scale-up.	Existing workforce requires additional training to either manufacture or deploy/install technology solution and pipelines exist to provide workforce training, but may need to be scaled.	Workforce is nearly non-existent, significant training is required for initial technology solution introduction and scale-up.

A.4 License To Operate

Risk Category	Readiness Value		
	High (7-9)	Medium (4-6)	Low (1-3)
Regulatory Environment	Technology solution can be broadly deployed within existing regulatory framework and standards, and those frameworks and standards are applied in a well-understood and fast-moving process with minimal risk of delays.	Technology solution can be broadly deployed with minor changes to regulations and standards, and / or regulatory hurdles are well understood but time-consuming and at risk of delays.	Technology solution can be broadly deployed only with major changes to regulations and standards or entirely new regulations and standards; or significant challenges exist to navigate existing regulations and standards.
Policy Environment	Technology solution requires little in the way of additional policy intervention to encourage adoption as a preferred solution; policymakers well aligned with any changes needed to encourage adoption.	Technology solution requires moderate policy intervention to achieve broad deployment and is well aligned with current governmental policy positions.	Technology solution requires significant policy intervention to achieve and / or sustain broad deployment; and / or policy makers are not aligned with implementing required intervention to encourage adoption.
Permitting & Siting	Permitting and siting process is easy, well-understood, timely, and repeatable.	Permitting and siting can be time consuming, but jurisdiction is clear, and complexity is low. Speed can be achieved with repetition.	Permitting and siting is highly complex and time-consuming, with multiple overlapping jurisdictions in play.
Environmental & Safety	Technology solution has minimal inherent environmental or safety risk; results in net zero carbon or negative carbon solution.	Technology solution has potential for environmental degradation and /or safety concerns, but the risks can be managed through current processes and / or anticipated future processes or solutions.	Technology solution has potential to create significant environmental degradation or increases carbon emissions over currently fielded solutions, and / or poses significant safety concerns that are challenging to mitigate.
Community Perception	Technology solution is likely to be positively received by the public with a strong level of support.	Technology solution may create pockets of public resistance but no systemic challenges are anticipated, and local communities are aligned with deployment in key deployment locations.	Technology solution is likely to generate negative public or community reactions that could derail or significantly delay deployment.

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